

Universal Design for Learning and Computer Science Education for Blind and Visually Impaired Students in Higher Education

A Systematic Literature Review

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Introduction

Higher Education is becoming more digital and data-driven, and Computer Science (CS) programmes play a central role in preparing students for future work and participation in society. However, blind and visually impaired students still face many barriers when they want to study CS in an inclusive way.

This report is an output of the Erasmus+ project “Access2CS – A Computer Science programme for visually and hearing-impaired students”. The project aims to make CS study programmes in Higher Education more accessible and inclusive for blind and visually impaired students.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) offers a helpful framework for this work. It suggests that teaching should use different ways to present information, to let students show what they have learned, and to support their motivation and participation. This is especially important in CS, where many subjects, tools and learning materials are very visual and therefore difficult to access for blind and visually impaired learners.

In this context, Access2CS conducted a systematic literature review on technologies and teaching methods that make CS education more accessible for blind and visually impaired students. The review looks at several CS domains, such as mathematics, programming, data visualisation and web development, and identifies barriers, existing guidance and proposed solutions that can support the design of more accessible CS materials and programmes.

1 Methodology

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1.1 Introduction

This section outlines the systematic approach taken in conducting the Access2CS literature review. The goal was to establish a clear, accountable, and transparent methodology, as recommended by Gough, Oliver, and Thomas (2012).

To inform the development of this review, several texts were consulted, including Kitchenham and Charters (2007), the EPPI-Centre (2006), Angela et al. (2022) and Kirwan et al. (2018). Kitchenham and Charters (2007) served as the primary guide, with the following steps adapted from Kitchenham and Charters presented as sub-headings to describe the workflow:

1. Specification of the Research Question
2. Development of a Review Protocol
3. Identification of Relevant Research
4. Selection of Primary Studies
5. Data Extraction and Monitoring

Additionally, the PRISMA flowchart (Moher et al., 2009) was used to visually map the flow of information through each stage of the systematic review process.

1.2 Specification of the Research Question

The PICOC framework (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, Context) was used to guide the formulation of the literature review questions and to develop the search string strategy (Kitchenham and Charters 2007).

	Description	PICOC example	Synonyms	Detailed keywords
Population	Can be a specific role, an application area, or an industry domain.	Blind students, Visually impaired students	STEM students	
Intervention	The methodology, tool, or technology that addresses a specific issue.	Support services, Teaching methods	Assistive technologies	Screen reader, braille displays
			Inclusive teaching methods	UDL, universal design, design for all/design4all
			Institutional support services	Learning centre, exam accommodations, service centres
			Emerging technologies	Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), Coding Assistants, Github, Copilot, Google, ML-Enhanced Code Completion
Comparison	The methodology, tool, or technology in which the <i>Intervention</i> is being compared (if appropriate).	Not applicable		
Outcome	Factors of importance to practitioners and/or the results that the <i>Intervention</i> could produce.	Accessibility	Barriers, Experiences, Guidance for teachers	
		Solutions		
Context	The context in which the comparison takes place.	Computer science Education	Third-level education, tertiary education, Higher Education, University college	

Table 1: PICOC framework (Kitchenham and Charters 2007)

The aim was to ensure that the body of reviewed literature collectively addressed the review questions (see below), rather than generating multiple, separate answers (Gough, Oliver, and Thomas, 2012).

- Which technologies and teaching methods have been used in making computer science education accessible for blind and visually impaired students?

The following Sub-section Review Question (SRQ) was also devised:

- RQ1. What are the existing barriers, guidance, and solutions for blind and visual-impaired students?

1.3 Development of a Review Protocol

A protocol was developed which included

- Selecting academic databases
- Documenting the search strings used against said databases.
- Defining inclusion/exclusion criteria

The following section, Identification of Research, provides a detailed account of these components.

1.4 Identification of Research

The selected databases included: Scopus, Web of Science, ACM Digital Library, and ERIC. These were chosen for their relevance to both education and computer science disciplines.

A search strategy was developed to achieve a balance between specificity - retrieving highly relevant studies - and sensitivity - ensuring broad coverage of the topic (EPPI Centre, 2006). Keywords including '*blind*', '*computer science*', '*assistive technology*', '*higher education*', and '*barrier*' were derived from the PICOC framework.

These keywords were then expanded using synonyms and logically structured using Boolean operators. An initial query (see below) was run on the Scopus database, which returned 1,638 articles. However, an early review of the retrieved articles revealed a high number of false positives, particularly due to ambiguous terms like "*blind*" and "*STEM*" (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics), which were frequently associated with blind studies in stem cell research—unrelated to the intended focus.

To address this, the search query was iteratively refined. The final version (Version 5) of the Scopus query is detailed below, incorporating additional filters and structural adjustments to improve precision:

```
(TITLE-ABS-KEY(( ( "visually impaired" OR "blind" OR "partially sighted" OR "low vision" )
AND ( "computer science" OR "computer science education" OR "programming" OR "coding"
OR STEM OR "applied science" ) AND ( "higher education" OR "universit*" OR "college" OR
"tertiary education" OR "third level" ) )) AND ABS(( "assistive technolog*" OR "screen reader*"
OR "braille" OR "universal design" OR "design for all" OR "inclusive education" OR "UDL" )
OR ( "teaching method*" OR "pedagog*" OR "instructional strateg*" OR "co-design" OR
"participatory" ) OR ( "barrier*" OR "challenge*" OR "experience*" OR "accommodation*" OR
"support service*" ) )) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE,"English" ) ) AND ( EXCLUDE (
DOCTYPE,"cr" ) ) AND ( EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA,"MEDI" ) OR EXCLUDE (
SUBJAREA,"NURS" ) OR EXCLUDE ( SUBJAREA,"HEAL" ) OR EXCLUDE (
SUBJAREA,"VETE" ) )
```

This refinement process was repeated – though to a lesser extent – across the other selected databases to further improve the accuracy and relevance of the search results. 1,694 articles were uploaded to the AI-SLR Rayyan Management software.

The final number of articles 1694, retrieved from each database is as follows.

Database	Type	Numbers
Scopus		82
ACM		1487
Web of Science		47
ERIC		78

Table 2: Number of Articles Retrieved

1.5 Selection of Primary Studies

A total of 48 articles were identified as potential duplicates, and 25 were subsequently verified and removed, leaving 1669 articles for abstract screening for relevance. The process is documented below.

1.5.1 Screening Workflow (using Rayyan)

The articles were randomly divided among five pairs of reviewers, with each pair assigned 334 articles, ensuring that each article was reviewed twice by the same two reviewers.

Reviewers were tasked with screening the title and abstract of each article based on the following research question:

"Which technologies and teaching methods have been used to make computer science education accessible for blind and visually impaired students at the third level?"

Articles were reviewed blindly in Rayyan's blinded mode, so that reviewers could not see each other's decisions.

1.5.2 Inclusion Criteria

While reviewing each article, reviewers assessed whether it addressed the following:

- Third-level (higher education)
- Computer Science or STEM students
- Blind or visually impaired students

For each assigned article, one of the following Rayyan labels was applied to the article

- Include – if the article clearly addresses all three criteria
- Exclude – if the article clearly does not address the criteria
- Maybe – if uncertain; in this case, add a note explaining your reasoning

At the conclusion of the screening process:

- The "blind review" option on Rayyan was disabled.
- Articles with conflicting decisions (i.e., disagreements between reviewers) were identified.
- Each reviewer was asked to resolve conflicts in their assigned articles in collaboration with their designated second reviewer.

All included articles were initially labelled as "Selected in Abstract Screening." As a result, the full text of 122 articles was uploaded to the Rayyan tool for further review. These were supplemented by 31 additional sources labelled as *grey literature*, which were selected by the team as important to include. This brought the total number of articles included in the full-text review to 157.

These articles were then divided among team members who categorised them into three themes: (1) Teachers: UDL, (2) Teachers: CS, and/or (3) Institutions. Some papers were classified under more than one theme. During this phase, some articles were further excluded as they did not meet the inclusion criteria.

An Excel file was created containing three corresponding sheets:

- Sheet 1 – Institutions: 29 papers
- Sheet 2 – Teachers: UDL: 69 papers
- Sheet 3 – Teachers: CS: 54 papers

These papers were then assigned to eleven team members for analysis. The three categories reflect the main perspectives of the review: institutional structures, teachers' use of UDL, and teachers' work in specific CS domains. While all three categories were screened and coded using the same methodology, this report focuses on the UDL- and CS-related findings; the analysis of the institutional studies will be presented in a separate report.

1.6 Data Extraction and Monitoring

To facilitate the thematic analysis of these papers, each reviewer was instructed to examine their assigned papers with the primary and sub-research questions in mind:

Which technologies and teaching methods have been used to make computer science education accessible for blind and visually impaired students? Additionally, they were asked to address two sub-questions: What are the existing barriers, available guidance, and proposed solutions for blind and visually impaired students?

Reviewers were asked to focus on how each paper addressed these questions and to capture their insights using the following headings.

Technologies; Barriers/Challenges (e.g., technological, social, or communicative); Methodology (including limitations and whether studies were tested at third level); Subject and Domain Problem (e.g., Software Engineering, UML); Pedagogical Approaches and Assessment; and Support, Services, or Training.

The authors summarised the findings from each paper using a structured template that focused on technologies, barriers, methodologies, pedagogical approaches and support structures.

Reviewers were also encouraged to identify and document other categories and relevant subcategories within the aforementioned themes.

Sixteen papers were subsequently removed during this process as not being relevant.

These summaries served as the basis for the literature review report. The process is documented below in a PRISMA Flow Document (Moher et al., 2009).

Figure 1: Prisma Flow Diagram (Moher et al., 2009)

2 Universal Design for Learning

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2.1 Introduction

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is an educational framework that promotes the design of teaching and learning environments that are accessible to diverse learners from the outset, rather than relying on individual accommodations added later. This perspective is particularly relevant in Computer Science (CS), where many subjects depend on visual representations, specialised software environments, and fast-paced interaction, all of which can create significant barriers for blind and visually impaired students.

Within the Access2CS project, UDL serves as an analytical lens to examine how information is presented (representation), how students interact with content and demonstrate learning (action and expression), and how teaching approaches support motivation and participation (engagement). The following sections therefore organise the findings of the systematic literature review according to UDL principles and across key CS domains (such as mathematics, programming, data visualisation, web development, and related subjects), in order to identify existing practices, barriers, and gaps.

2.2 Methodology

The results are presented by subject or domain, as covered by the reviewed research papers. A total of 63 papers are included in this analysis, grouped according to their Computer Science-related domain.

Only one paper offered a holistic perspective recommending UDL as a broad framework to improve inclusion (Moore & Urness, 2024). This contribution remained at a high-level, outlining the general UDL principles. Stefik et al. (2019) provided a wider review of accessibility challenges in CS education, examining more specific examples. These challenges included: inaccessible course content, inaccessible coding language IDEs, inaccessible assessments (involving visual content), challenges faced by blind students creating materials for assessments, barriers in mathematics, limited staff capacity and skillset limitations among teaching staff, and inconsistencies across standards (e.g., Nemeth and UEB Braille).

Several papers then examined these barriers within specific domains, for example in mathematics (Karshmer et al., 1998; Cervone & Sorge, 2019; Arooj et al., 2021; Kruger et al., 2023) and programming (Schanzer et al., 2019; Ferrari & Hurst, 2021).

For each domain, we present an overview structured around categories derived from the three core UDL principles:

1. Representation: how is information presented to students?
 - a. Technologies: A key component of UDL is providing multiple means of representation. Assistive tools, tactile systems, and accessible formats directly support perception and interaction.
 - b. Blind/Low-Vision: Clarifies the stakeholders considered across the reviewed research papers, identifying whether interventions target blind learners, low-vision learners, or both.
2. Action and Expression: how do students interact and demonstrate learning?
 - a. Methodology: This category contextualises and validate the research findings.
 - b. Barriers/Challenges: UDL encourages the identification and proactive removal of barriers to learning, rather than retrofitting solutions after challenges arise.
3. Engagement: how are students motivated and supported?
 - a. Pedagogical approach: Demonstrates how the described tools or teaching strategies are implemented to support inclusive learning experiences.
 - b. Support and training: Reflects UDL's emphasis on learner variability and institutional responsibility, including training, guidance, and infrastructure required to implement accessible practices at scale.

Each domain concludes with a synthesis of the reviewed literature, summarising key approaches, identifying recurring accessibility challenges, and noting practical considerations and gaps where highlighted in the research.

The chapter concludes with an overall synthesis of UDL-related findings across domains, drawing together cross-cutting patterns and limitations within the current evidence base.

2.3 Mathematics

2.3.1 Representation

Accessing mathematics non-visually requires precise and structured representation. Researchers have explored several approaches to improve spoken mathematics clarity and to enable tactile and auditory learning. For example, Souza and Freitas (2020) introduced a prosodic model aligned with MathML to improve the naturalness and intelligibility of synthesised mathematical speech. Murphy et al. (2010) experimented with spatialized audio cues and spearcons to reduce ambiguity in mathematical expressions.

Many of the papers consider the UDL principles of Representation, Action, and Expression together. They examine ways of providing accessible course notes while also facilitating ways in which the student can create content to express their knowledge of the subject. Typically, they regard both processes as two sides of the same challenge (Karshmer et al., 1998; Cervone & Sorge, 2019; Arooj et al., 2021; Kruger et al., 2023).

These papers focus on bridging the gap between formats the mathematics teachers can use (primarily LaTeX) and accessible formats the students can perceive, such as Braille and Nemeth Math (Karshmer et al., 1998) or MathML, which can be rendered in accessible ways (Arooj et al., 1998, Cervone & Sorge, 2019). By providing perceptible mathematical notation, the UDL principle of Representation is addressed.

Accessing course notes is only one aspect of representation. Students also need to be able to express their knowledge in ways assessors can understand. Therefore, these papers also examine converting students' mathematical work back into LaTeX for assessment purposes (Karshmer et al., 1998; Arooj et al., 2021; Cervone & Sorge, 2019; Kruger et al., 2023).

Additionally, Ariza & Hernández (2015) and Papasalouros & Tsolomitis (2015) addressed the conversion of printed mathematical content into Braille using LaTeX-to-Braille pipelines and MathML output, enabling learners to perceive structure in symbolic notation tactilely or audibly.

2.3.1.1 Technologies:

Technologies play a central role in supporting multiple means of representation in mathematics. Key tools include:

- Speech-based rendering systems (Souza & Freitas, 2020; Murphy et al., 2010) that use spatial and prosodic cues to represent mathematical structure.
- MathJax JavaScript library, including new accessibility features described and evaluated by Cervone & Sorge (2019).
- MathML and LaTeX-to-Braille converters, including tools such as ChattyInfty and Lambda Editor (Karshmer et al., 1998; Papasalouros & Tsolomitis, 2015; Cervone & Sorge, 2019; Arooj et al., 2021; Kruger et al., 2023).
- Talking calculators such as the Orion TI-30XS and TI-84 Plus, combined with sonographs for graphing functions (Papasalouros & Tsolomitis, 2015).
- Math-aware OCR systems and Braille-compatible notations (Másilko & Pecl, 2013; Ribera et al., 2013), which automate translation from visual mathematics into accessible formats.

2.3.1.2 Blind/Low-Vision

Most systems primarily targeted completely blind users, particularly those using screen readers (Karshmer et al., 1998; Cervone & Sorge, 2019; Arooj et al., 2021; Kruger et al., 2023).

Some interventions, such as the DAISY pipeline tools and screen magnification tools discussed in Másilko & Pecl (2013), offer hybrid support for low-vision learners who benefit from both visual and tactile representations.

However, low-vision users remain comparatively underserved in mathematics-specific studies. The majority of research focuses on fully blind participants rather than addressing the variability of visual impairment, which is central to UDL principles.

2.3.2 Action and Expression

2.3.2.1 Methodology

Cervone & Sorge (2019) adopted a descriptive approach in which features of the latest version of MathJax were described and discussed, including how it can be used alongside new personalisation features. They used some functional testing. Karshmer et al. (1998) built a prototype and tested functionality, however, this testing did not involve blind or visually impaired users.

While some early prototype work did not include blind participants, most of the later studies involved blind and visually impaired users directly in the evaluation process. Typically, they used Action research approaches (Arooj et al., 2019), for example building an accessible LaTeX editor and then conducting user testing with blind users. Observation and reflective feedback further informed the testing activities. Similarly, Kruger et al. (2023) tested their browsing approach with blind users.

Murphy et al. (2010) conducted an online auditory survey with 56 participants (21 visually impaired) to examine the effectiveness of different non-speech audio cues for presenting mathematical content. Souza and Freitas (2020) analysed teacher speech using audio processing software (Praat and FujiparaEditor), although their prosodic model lacked direct testing with blind learners. Several UDL-focused papers conducted technical evaluations of OCR conversion systems, user testing with Braille output, and software compatibility analysis (for example, Papasalouros & Tsolomitis (2015) and Másilko & Pecl (2013)).

Kruger et al. (2023) proposed a browsing approach to mathematical content for print-disabled readers. The browsing approach was evaluated by 11 blind and 14 sighted participants in a user trial that included identifying twelve equations extracted from PDF documents.

2.3.2.2 Barriers/Challenges:

As mentioned, there are differences between the formats mathematics teachers can understand, (namely LaTeX) and accessible formats the students can perceive, such as Braille and Nemeth Math (Karshner et al., 1998) or MathML, which can be rendered in ways the students perceive (Arooj et al., 1998; Cervone & Sorge, 2019).

Navigation through mathematical equations is also an issue. Kruger et al. (2023) offered an approach that draws on navigational mechanisms often used to explore the virtual worlds of text-adventure games, with audio-visual sensory substitution for graphical content. The virtual world allows the reader to interactively discover the spatial structure of the equation, while the rendition of graphical elements as sound allows the shape and identity of elements that cannot be synthesised as speech to be discovered and recognised.

Auditory math often struggles to convey the spatial and hierarchical nature of equations, leading to ambiguity and cognitive overload (Murphy et al., 2010). Braille notations require consistency in formatting, which remains difficult with automated tools. Additionally, users face challenges in distinguishing nested expressions or navigating mathematical content linearly using screen readers without enhanced prosodic or structural support (Souza & Freitas, 2020; Papasalouros & Tsolomitis, 2015).

2.3.3 Engagement

2.3.3.1 Pedagogical Approach

Instructional strategies aligned with UDL emphasised multisensory engagement. Several studies advocated for layered audio cues, tactile exploration, and simultaneous Braille/audio output to facilitate abstract mathematical reasoning. Wolfram Language and MathML-rendered speech were incorporated into interactive activities to enhance learner agency (Papasalouros & Tsolomitis, 2015; Ribera et al., 2013). Tools such as AccessLecture (Abu Doush et al., 2009) supported real-time engagement with mathematical content during class.

2.3.3.2 Support and Training:

These tools often include support features such as:

- Onboarding materials for using speech-based mathematics tools.
- Standardized Braille templates and voice command instructions.
- Tutorials and best practice guides for educators on how to integrate accessible mathematics into coursework (Másilko & Pecl, 2013; Ribera et al., 2013).

However, many studies noted the lack of formal training in these systems among teachers, creating a gap in effective classroom deployment.

2.3.4 Summary & Recommendations

There are many ways to make mathematics accessible nowadays, particularly when working with digital materials, as this allows students to access materials using their own devices and screen readers. However, understanding standard LaTeX notation through these tools remains very difficult. JavaScript libraries such as MathJax help to both write and render mathematical equations in more accessible ways. There are also tools that directly translate these equations into Braille – if the student has access to a Braille display or to a Braille printer – such as ChattyInfty and Lambda Editor.

Based on the literature reviewed in this chapter, accessibility in mathematics is most effective when mathematical content is created and delivered in structured digital formats that can be converted across modalities (speech, Braille, and visual notation). Supporting the use of tools such as MathJax and LaTeX-to-Braille converters can help bridge the gap between lecturer-authored materials and student access. At the same time, additional work is still needed to improve the readability and navigation of standard LaTeX notation for screen reader users.

2.4 Data Visualisation

2.4.1 Representation

Although data visualisation is often taught alongside mathematics, it involves distinct cognitive processes and accessibility requirements that warrant separate consideration. While mathematics typically centres on symbolic reasoning and linear expressions, data visualisation focuses on the interpretation of spatial relationships, trends, and patterns presented through charts and graphs. For blind and visually impaired learners, accessing these two domains requires different assistive technologies, such as MathML and prosodic speech for mathematics, versus tactile graphics and sonification for data visualisation. Given these differences in representation, tools, and learning strategies, this review treats data visualisation as a separate domain to highlight its unique challenges and solutions.

Non-visual representation of data has advanced through tactile graphics, audio descriptions, and interactive multimodal interfaces. The Graph Sketching Tool (GSK) by Balik et al. (2014) enabled blind users to explore and construct node-link diagrams through screen reader-compatible navigation, while TPad (Melfi et al., 2020) combined tactile overlays and audio feedback for real-time diagram exploration. More recently, Chart4Blind (Moured et al., 2024) used AI to convert bitmap charts into text descriptions and tactile renderings, allowing users to perceive axes, labels, and data trends independently. SonoGraphs and LoggerPro (Isaacson et al., 2016) introduced sonification as an auditory alternative to visual data charts.

2.4.1.1 Technologies

The following technologies were central to enabling accessible data visualisation:

- Chart4Blind: Integrates D3.js for visualisation, Mask2Former for segmentation, and Tesseract OCR for text extraction; runs in-browser for ease of access (Moured et al., 2024).
- Screen Readers and chart-access tools: Including Chart Reader, alt text, ARIA, sonification approaches, web standards, audio graphs, Highcharts, Microsoft Power BI, SAS Graphics Accelerator, and Tableau. Visualisation grammar-based tools such as Vega-Lite are also discussed (Thompson et al., 2023).
- Graph Sketching Tool (GSK): Built with Java Swing and Java Access Bridge, fully screen reader compatible (Balik et al., 2014).
- TPad: Uses 3D-printed tactile graphics and iPad gesture input (Melfi et al., 2020).
- LoggerPro & SonoGraphs: Enable sonification of scientific data (Isaacson et al., 2016).

- Tactile Graphics Helper (TGH) and Dynamic Graph prototype (Abu Doush et al., 2009; Fusco & Morash, 2015): Combine finger tracking, machine vision, and force-feedback haptics to support dynamic graph exploration.

2.4.1.2 Blind/Low-Vision

Most data visualisation tools were developed specifically for blind users. The tactile-first orientation of TPad, GSK, and Chart4Blind was informed by user feedback from blind participants. Some tools (e.g., LoggerPro, TGH) also offered functionality for low-vision users through auditory supplements or magnification-compatible interfaces (Ariza & Hernández, 2015; Isaacson et al., 2016).

In addition to developing chart-reading technology, Thompson et al. (2023) provide a comprehensive review of alternative representations and important information that must be considered when designing accessible charts. Their work also offers a detailed evaluation of alternative means of representation and discusses a wide range of relevant technologies for accessible data visualisation.

2.4.2 Action and Expression

2.4.2.1 Methodology

Balik et al. (2014) employed task-based testing with screen reader users to validate the Graph Sketching Tool (GSK). Melfi et al. (2020) conducted comparative evaluations across three systems with five blind students. Moured et al. (2024) used a mixed-method design: ten sighted participants completed tasks using Chart4Blind, which was also evaluated by accessibility experts through interviews. Isaacson et al. (2016) included field testing of LoggerPro in school lab settings with blind learners, alongside compatibility validation with JAWS.

Thompson et al. (2023) used a co-design approach with screen reader users (10 blind and low-vision design partners – 7 males, 3 females – from Microsoft) to develop Chart Reader.

3.4.2.2 Barriers/Challenges

Common challenges include:

- Manual tactile production is costly and time-consuming (Melfi et al., 2020).
- Lack of standardization in tactile chart formats (Balik et al., 2014).
- High cognitive load when interpreting complex data relationships non-visually.
- Limited tool exposure among students and educators (Fusco & Morash, 2015).
- Multimodal conflicts between screen readers and custom tactile interfaces (Moured et al., 2024).
- Inaccessible charts, difficulties navigating charts, poor alternative text, and challenges in understanding data (Thompson et al., 2023).

2.4.3 Engagement

2.4.3.1 Pedagogical approach

Instructional strategies relied on learner-led exploration and hands-on engagement. Students used these tools to independently read, interpret, and create graphs, fostering agency in STEM-related tasks. In classroom settings, LoggerPro's sonification features allowed blind students to engage with real-time experimental data alongside their sighted peers (Isaacson et al., 2016). Activities emphasised comparative exploration across visual and non-visual modalities.

2.4.3.2 Support and training

Most tools incorporated in-app guidance, tactile legends, or gesture-based prompts. For example, TPad used tap-activated audio labels on tactile overlays. Chart4Blind included automatic chart calibration and cheat sheet. Training materials and assistive guides were crucial, particularly where multimodal interfaces required onboarding (Melfi et al., 2020; Abu Doush et al., 2009; Papasalouros & Tsolomitis, 2015).

2.4.4 Summary & Recommendations

The literature reviewed demonstrates a range of approaches to accessible data visualisation, including tactile graphics, sonification, and multimodal interfaces that support non-visual interpretation of charts and graphs. Tools such as Graph Sketching Tool, TPad, Chart4Blind, and LoggerPro show how users can explore and create data visualisations through auditory and tactile means. However, challenges remain around standardisation, production time for tactile materials, and compatibility between multimodal tools and screen readers.

Current research points to a huge gap in this field. Much of the work identified is older and now inaccessible, meaning that new research on this topic is needed. Based on this review, accessible data visualisation is most effective when multimodal representations are used. At the same time, further research is needed to update existing tools, improve interoperability, and expand awareness and use of accessible visualisation technologies in educational contexts.

2.5 Programming

2.5.1 Representation

Accessible programming instruction has emphasised multimodal representations to support learners who are blind or visually impaired. Textual code was paired with screen reader-friendly editors and tools such as StructJumper – an Eclipse plugin that supports semantic navigation of code blocks (Baker, 2017). Physical aids, such as tactile code structure diagrams and audio-annotated line-by-line walkthroughs, allowed learners to understand indentation, hierarchy, and logic flow.

2.5.1.1 Technologies

Key programming accessibility technologies included:

- StructJumper: A plugin that allows blind users to navigate code using keyboard shortcuts mapped to code structures (Baker, 2017).
- Accessible IDEs: Eclipse and Repl.it, paired with screen readers such as JAWS or NVDA.
- Accessible Programming with Quorum (Stefik et al., 2019; Ferrari & Hurst 2021).
- CodeMirror Blocks (Schanzer et al., 2019).
- Tactile representations of code syntax and structures, used in introductory training (Ferrari et al., 2021).
- MATLAB for blind users: Leveraging built-in sonification and structural code output (Baker, 2017).
- Keyboard-based simulators for programming logic, particularly in early learning contexts (Armstrong, 2009).

2.5.1.2 Blind/Low-Vision

The target population for most programming interventions was blind learners, particularly those with no previous coding experience (Ferrari et al., 2021, 2023). Although some tools,

such as StructJumper and MATLAB, could support low-vision users through screen magnification or contrast modes, these features were underemphasised. This indicates a broader need to address the hybrid accessibility needs of low-vision users in programming education.

2.5.2 Action and Expression

2.5.2.1 Methodology

Ferrari et al. (2021, 2023) applied a comprehensive mixed-methods framework involving pre- and post-tests, interviews, and tutor feedback across a nine-week workshop. Baker (2017) evaluated StructJumper's usability with blind learners using observational and survey-based methods. Usability testing of MATLAB for blind students was discussed in terms of code tracing and real-time debugging accuracy.

Observational studies were frequently applied, where participants were given programming tasks using the new environment and observations were recorded. Reflective feedback was also noted (Stefik et al., 2019; Schanzer et al., 2019; Ferrari et al., 2021).

2.5.2.2 Barriers/Challenges

Significant barriers in programming accessibility include:

- Inadequate screen reader support in mainstream IDEs, particularly for identifying errors, indentation, and nested structures (Stefik et al., 2019; Schanzer et al. 2019; Ferrari et al., 2021).
- Inaccessible programming Assessments using inaccessible IDEs (Stefik et al., 2019; Schanzer et al. 2019).
- Visual heavy syntax representations, such as color-coded CSS or JavaScript logic, which are particularly difficult to access (Ferrari et al., 2021).
- Limited accessible debugging tools, requiring workarounds or peer support.
- Cognitive load associated with navigating large codebases without structural shortcuts or semantic markers (Baker, 2017).
- Challenges navigating program structure, especially tree structures used in debugging (Stefik et al., 2019; Schanzer et al., 2019; Ferrari et al., 2021).

2.5.3 Engagement

2.5.3.1 Pedagogical approach

Instruction was typically project-based and exploratory. Ferrari et al. (2021, 2023) emphasised scaffolded assignments, beginning with accessible HTML pages and progressing to JavaScript logic and user interaction. StructJumper and MATLAB tasks were designed to reinforce structural understanding and promote problem-solving via non-visual cues. Emphasis was placed on transferable real-world skills, including building live websites and engaging in code reviews.

2.5.3.2 Support and training

Mentoring and structured support were critical to success. Weekly one-on-one sessions, tactile starter kits, and remote labs enabled learners to progress independently. StructJumper included guided documentation, while MATLAB support came with built-in sonification documentation. Training materials addressed command-line workflows and editor customization to match screen reader preferences (Baker, 2017; Ferrari et al., 2023).

2.5.4 Summary & Recommendations

To create accessible programming instructions, general accessibility principles must be followed. In addition, programming-specific challenges – such as navigating large codebases and debugging complex structures – must be taken into account. Sufficient supervision and peer support are also important to enable effective participation.

IDEs such as Visual Studio Code, when used with appropriate extensions, are now relatively screen reader-friendly and allow blind and low-vision individuals to participate in coding exercises alongside their peers.

Based on the literature reviewed in this section, accessible programming is most effective when mainstream tools are adapted with appropriate accessibility extensions and when structured support mechanisms are in place. Continued attention to navigation, debugging accessibility, and screen reader compatibility remains necessary.

2.6 Modelling and Diagramming

2.6.1 Representation

Unified Modelling Language (UML) diagrams are widely employed in Systems Analysis and Design (SAaD) courses to convey intricate concepts, structures, and workflows. Although various tools aim to support blind and visually impaired users in working with UML diagrams, many still lack sufficient functionality to allow independent creation and modification. As a result, blind and visually impaired students often face barriers to full participation in collaborative and peer-feedback activities that rely on visual representations.

Carruthers et al. (2023) examine the potential of PlantUML to address these accessibility challenges. Their experience report outlines how a SAaD course was adapted using readily available tools (specifically PlantUML) to make course activities accessible for a screen reader user while promoting full inclusion of all students in collaborative and feedback-based learning.

PlantUML allows for a text-based representation of modelling diagrams from Computer Science, including UML diagrams, network diagrams, and tree diagrams. These diagrams can be converted into graphical images and back again. This provides a way for blind students to both read and write diagrams across various computer science topics, including networking, algorithms, security, and data and system modelling.

2.6.1.1 Technologies

- PlantUML: A text-based diagramming tool that enables UML and related modelling diagrams to be authored and rendered from textual descriptions.

2.6.1.2 Blind/Low-Vision

The reviewed work primarily focuses on blind users, particularly screen reader users who benefit from text-based diagram creation and navigation. The text-based structure of PlantUML supports screen reader compatibility, enabling blind students to engage with modelling content. The specific needs of low-vision users are not extensively addressed in the reviewed material.

2.6.2 Action and Expression

2.6.2.1 Methodology

The reported approach involved co-design, reflection, and feedback from sighted and non-sighted students and instructors.

3.6.2.2 Barriers/Challenges

Barriers identified include:

- Inaccessible software engineering diagrams, particularly in data modelling contexts.
- Difficulties for blind students in creating graphical content required for Software Engineering classes.

2.6.3 Engagement

2.6.3.1 Pedagogical approach

Ensuring that visual design tasks are both accessible and inclusive benefits all participants, not only those with visual impairments, by fostering diversity of thought and creativity throughout the iterative design process.

PlantUML serves as an Enabler allowing blind students to create UML and other diagrams such as trees and networks in formats lecturers understand and vice versa. It has an accessible text editor which works well with a screen reader. Text-based enables students to engage in diagram creation, modification, and review processes alongside their peers.

2.6.3.2 Support and training

Support was provided through the adaptation of course materials and activities to make diagramming tasks accessible for screen reader users. The use of PlantUML's accessible text editor enabled students to work with modelling diagrams in formats compatible with assistive technologies.

However, adapting diagram-based course content required additional time and effort to convert existing materials into accessible formats.

2.6.4 Summary & Recommendations

Systems Analysis and Design can be taught more inclusively by supplementing course materials with accessible diagrams. These can be created in PlantUML, which provides both a textual representation of diagrams and a graphical rendering. This allows students to view and create modelling diagrams through a textual interface that is compatible with screen readers.

Text-based diagramming approaches support participation in modelling and diagramming activities that would otherwise rely on visual representations. However, adapting existing diagram-based materials requires additional time and effort to convert documents into accessible formats.

2.7 Web Development

2.7.1 Representation

Web development learning for blind students has benefited from highly structured and multimodal instructional designs. Ferrari et al. (2021, 2023) demonstrated that HTML, CSS, and JavaScript could be effectively taught using a combination of screen reader-friendly editors, tactile guides, and one-on-one support. Instructional content was presented via accessible web editors (for example, Repl.it with ARIA compliance), tactile handouts describing page layout, and real-time screen reader feedback. Students developed mental models of the Document Object Model (DOM) using tactile diagrams, reinforcing conceptual understanding through physical exploration.

2.7.1.1 Technologies

Accessible web development was supported by the following tools:

- Screen reader-compatible coding environments such as Repl.it and Eclipse with StructJumper plugin (Baker, 2007).
- Tactile HTML/CSS guides created via swell paper or 3D-printed layouts (Ferrari et al., 2021).
- Remote mentoring platforms (Zoom, shared screen with audio descriptions).
- Speech-based navigation tools and Braille-compatible web editors.
- Assistive toolkits with cheat sheets, semantic markup samples, and command line scaffolds (Ferrari et al., 2023; Baker, 2017).
- Mathematics representation for the Web using MathJAx (Cervone & Sorge 2019).

2.7.1.2 Blind/Low-Vision

The workshops and interventions were tailored primarily to blind adults with no prior coding experience (Ferrari et al., 2021, 2023). In earlier work in Uganda, some low-vision students also participated (Ferrari et al., 2019), and accommodations were made with screen magnification tools and simplified visual interfaces.

2.7.2 Action and Expression

2.7.2.1 Methodology

Ferrari et al. (2021) used a mixed-methods approach, including pre- and post-course surveys, quizzes, interviews, and tutor feedback, across a nine-week training program for 12 blind students. Ferrari et al. (2019) applied a similar model during a one-week intensive training in

Uganda, combining direct observation, surveys, and focus groups. Baker (2017) complemented this with tool-level evaluations, assessing screen reader responsiveness and Integrated Development Environment (IDE) compatibility.

2.7.2.2 Barriers/Challenges

Participants encountered major barriers with colour-dependent feedback in CSS, inaccessible layout tools, and limited IDE screen reader support – especially for interpreting indentation, nesting, or spatial relationships in code (Ferrari et al., 2021). Producing tactile diagrams was also time-intensive and costly. Furthermore, many learners lacked prior exposure to programming logic or computational thinking, adding cognitive complexity to the task.

2.7.3 Engagement

2.7.3.1 Pedagogical approach

Instructional design was heavily learner-centred and project-based. Students were encouraged to build personal portfolios and deploy real-world websites. Assignments were scaffolded to support sequential skill development, progressing from simple HTML pages to interactive JavaScript components (Ferrari et al., 2023). Learning tasks involved direct manipulation, code tracing, and feedback loops aligned with UDL principles of engagement and action.

2.7.3.2 Support and training

Weekly one-on-one sessions with teaching assistants, remote synchronous labs, and asynchronous resources (e.g., tutorials, recordings) were core to the program's success. The use of onboarding sessions and tactile starter kits (with Braille labels and orientation cues) supported learners become independent when working on complex web design tasks. The StructJumper tool (Baker, 2017) enabled navigation across HTML structures using keyboard commands mapped to DOM logic.

2.7.4 Summary & Recommendations

The technical aspects of web development (HTML and JavaScript) can be taught by providing accessible digital materials, including sufficient alternative information, and by working with screen reader-friendly tools such as Visual Studio Code with appropriate plugins. This approach can be supplemented with tactile guides, where possible.

For the design aspects (CSS), accessibility presents additional challenges. Layouts and functionalities can be supported through tangible guides, such as small physical models or materials printed on tactile paper.

Accessible web development is most effective when structured digital tools are combined with tactile supports and guided instruction. Attention should continue to be given to improving accessibility in design-focused components, particularly those that rely heavily on visual layout and colour-based feedback.

2.8 Science, Physics and Electronics

2.8.1 Representation

Representation of science, physics, and electronics content for blind and visually impaired learners relies heavily on multimodal approaches. Across the literature, tactile, auditory, and sonification formats are used to convey spatial, graphical, and data-driven concepts that are typically presented visually. These approaches aim to support access to diagrams, scientific data, and technical illustrations that are central to STEM learning.

2.8.1.1 Technologies

Science content for blind and visually impaired learners has increasingly leveraged multimodal representation formats. Tactile, auditory, and sonification strategies dominate efforts to make complex scientific and technical concepts accessible. For instance, TPad overlays 3D-printed tactile elements on tablet screens with double-tap audio output (Melfi et al., 2020), allowing students to explore spatial concepts such as circuit diagrams and biology schematics. Similarly, Chart4Blind (Moured et al., 2024) translates bitmap line charts into structured text and tactile formats. Sonification tools such as LoggerPro and MATLAB functions (Isaacson et al., 2016) offer alternative modalities to understand trends in scientific data.

A wide range of tools support STEM accessibility. These include:

- Sonification platforms (LoggerPro, SonoGraphs, MATLAB): Enabling auditory interpretation of numerical data (Isaacson et al., 2016).
- Tactile and haptic devices: The Dynamic Graph prototype (Fusco & Morash, 2015), Tactile Graphics Helper (TGH) with voice interaction and finger tracking (Ariza & Hernández, 2015), and the Novint Falcon haptic device simulate friction, force, and spatial gradients.
- Recording technologies (Ariza & Hernández, 2015) and VictorReader Stream (Armstrong, 2009) support multimodal content access, especially for blind learners.
- Tactile drawing boards, pegboards, raised-line rendering printers, and QR-code-enhanced materials (Braier et al., 2014; Fusco & Morash, 2015; Melfi et al., 2022, Race et al. 2023) provide ways to navigate diagrams, flowcharts, and STEM illustrations.

2.8.1.2 Blind/Low-Vision

Most interventions were designed for blind users and tested with this population (e.g., Melfi et al., 2020, 2022; Ferrari et al., 2019). A minority of studies accounted for low-vision needs by supporting magnification, high-contrast displays, and hybrid tactile-visual interfaces (Ludi et al., 2012; Braier et al., 2014; Abu Doush et al., 2009; Fusco & Morash, 2015). However, this remains an area with limited coverage in STEM-specific interventions.

One of the major challenges in STEM content is the use of colour to convey meaning, for example in charts, graphs, and maps. Arauja et al. (2021) examine how colour can be represented tactically using the See Color Scheme. See Color is a colour-coding system based on Braille writing, designed to communicate colours to people with visual impairments. This study assessed the perception of the theme “Temperature” by blind participants using the See Color code on two isarithmic tactile maps, alongside comparison with participants with typical colour vision.

2.8.2 Action and Expression

2.8.2.1 Methodology

Studies employed mixed-method designs, including task-based usability testing (Melfi et al., 2020, 2022), observational case studies, and expert interviews (Abu et al., 2009, Fusco & Morash, 2015). For example, Ferrari et al. (2019) used surveys and focus groups with blind students during intensive STEM training in Uganda. LoggerPro was evaluated using compatibility testing with the JAWS screen reader, alongside real-time student interactions in STEM labs (Isaacson et al., 2016). Other tools, such as tactile simulation devices, were validated via structured user walkthroughs and iterative prototyping.

2.8.2.2 Barriers/Challenges

Persistent challenges include the high cost and slow production of tactile materials, lack of mainstream tool integration, and steep learning curves for both students and educators (Melfi et al., 2020; Ariza & Hernández, 2015). Many tools require teacher facilitation or prior tactile literacy, limiting learner autonomy. In addition, diagrams and complex graphs remain difficult to standardise across subjects, resulting in fragmented adoption.

One major challenge is the creation of accessible graphics as part of coursework, for example the design of tactile graphics within team projects or within assessments. Blind designers are underrepresented in the field of tactile graphic design, where sighted designers routinely control the process and output on their behalf. This lack of representation is linked to inaccessible digital technologies that prevent the non-visual design of tactile graphics by blind designers.

Race et al. (2023) explore tactile graphic design with a blind-led team of four blind designers, one sighted designer, and one sighted researcher. Issues identified include inaccessible drawing technology (e.g., CAD systems), expensive accessible design tools, AI tools not yet reaching their full potential, differences between tactile and visual design workflows, the representation of colour in tactile graphics, and challenges in scaling tactile design. Race et al. (2023) make several recommendations regarding inclusive workflows which would have broad impact on improving the participation of blind and visually impaired students in assessment activities.

2.8.3 Engagement

2.8.3.1 Pedagogical approach

Teaching strategies emphasised hands-on, experiential learning, in line with UDL principles of engagement. Ferrari et al. (2019) and Melfi et al. (2020) used tactile aids to scaffold spatial reasoning. UDL-focused tools (such as those described in Abu et al., 2009) promoted active learning by enabling real-time exploration, note-taking, and content manipulation during STEM classes. Sonification tools encouraged exploration through auditory pattern recognition, useful for visually analysing trends in scientific data.

Many of the recommendations that are offered by Race et al. (2023) focus on more inclusive workflows to increase participation. They highlight technology as an enabler of meaningful learning activities and emphasise that accessibility is necessary to facilitate engagement.

2.8.3.2 Support and training

Sustained support emerged as critical for effective STEM access. Many interventions provided audio tutorials, tactile legends, onboarding documentation, and teacher training. For example, LoggerPro was adapted to pair with screen readers and included training protocols for both students and instructors (Isaacson et al., 2016). Ferrari et al. (2021) emphasised the need for scaffolding materials such as tactile guides with Braille labels and orientation markers.

2.8.4 Summary & Recommendations

As science is a broad field, approaches to representation vary across sub-disciplines. The representation of content depends heavily on the type of material being taught, particularly where diagrams, graphs, and technical illustrations are involved. Making study materials digitally available and ensuring that documents follow accessibility guidelines remains one of the most effective ways to improve access.

For inherently visual representations – such as images in general, plots, and graphs – alternative textual descriptions should be provided. There are also ways to make graphs and plots digitally accessible through the use of tools like PlantUML.

The literature reviewed in this section highlights that accessibility in STEM is not only dependent on the availability of tools, but also on the design workflows through which graphical and scientific materials are created. Inclusive approaches to tactile graphic design, particularly those involving blind designers, demonstrate the importance of accessible production processes in supporting participation in coursework and assessment. Continued attention is therefore needed to both the tools used and the workflows through which accessible STEM materials are developed.

2.9 Networking

2.9.1 Representation

In the reviewed literature, networking concepts – such as data flow, topology, and system interactions – were presented through tactile simulations and auditory command-line environments. Given the abstract and often spatial nature of network infrastructure, accessible simulation platforms enabled learners to explore concepts through sequential auditory feedback and keyboard-controlled environments. Virtual labs and text-based environments substituted graphical interfaces with structured output and linear workflows (Armstrong, 2009; Omiegbe, 2024).

2.9.1.1 Technologies

Accessible networking instruction utilised:

- Command-line-based simulators designed for keyboard navigation without requiring visual input (Armstrong, 2009).
- Tactile representations using pegboards, dominos, and wire to build physical models of networks (Armstrong, 2009).
- Screen enlargers and contrast controls for low-vision users (Ariza & Hernández, 2015).

2.9.1.2 Blind/Low-Vision

Both blind and low-vision learners were included in the research. While blind learners relied primarily on-screen readers and tactile tools, low-vision learners benefited from tools such as MAGic screen magnification, large-print overlays, and contrast-adjusted virtual interfaces (Ariza & Hernández, 2015; Armstrong, 2009).

However, many systems were originally optimised for blind users, with comparatively less consideration given to the hybrid accessibility needs of low-vision students.

2.9.2 Action and Expression

2.9.2.1 Methodology

Ludi et al. (2012) collected requirements via surveys and interviews from 11 low-vision students and 8 instructors to guide the development of more inclusive technologies. Armstrong 2009 and Omiegbe (2024) conducted prototype testing of virtual labs and command-line simulators, with user feedback collected through observations, task-based evaluations, and heuristic analyses.

2.9.2.2 Barriers/Challenges

- Graphical network visualisations are rarely screen reader accessible.
- High cognitive demand when simulating abstract networking concepts without visual aids (Armstrong, 2009).
- Lack of curricular integration, with few accessible networking modules embedded in standard CS syllabi.
- Resource constraints, such as limited availability of haptic or physical simulation kits (Armstrong, 2009, Ludi et al., 2012).

2.9.3 Engagement

2.9.3.1 Pedagogical approach

Simulation-based, inquiry-driven learning approaches were employed. Learners engaged with tactile kits and accessible command-line simulators to construct, test, and troubleshoot virtual networks. Activities emphasised procedural reasoning and problem-solving through non-visual modalities. Collaboration with peers was sometimes integrated through shared audio environments and accessible chat clients.

2.9.3.2 Support and training

Limited formal training was reported. However, Armstrong (2009) recommended development of tailored learning modules and structured orientation materials for accessible networking labs. Ludi et al. (2012) suggested that accessible simulation platforms should be accompanied by teacher guides and usability documentation to ensure integration into mainstream Computer Science classrooms.

2.9.4 Summary & Recommendations

Creating accessible materials for a networking course can be challenging, but not impossible. Workarounds are required when representing network structures, which often can be difficult to interpret, even for sighted learners. Tactile models can be deployed to support understanding, although these need to be custom-built.

Alternatively, tools such as PlantUML could be used to create accessible diagrammatic representations through custom components. However, this approach has not yet been widely deployed within networking classroom settings.

Accessible networking instruction benefits from the use of command-line environments, tactile simulations, and structured virtual laboratories. Greater integration of these approaches into mainstream curricula, alongside further exploration of accessible diagramming workflows, would support broader participation in networking education.

2.10 Accessible educational material

2.10.1 Representation

Creating accessible educational materials involves delivering content in structured, multimodal formats – particularly in text-heavy or visually complex domains. Tools such as A11yBoard (Zhang et al., 2023) allowed blind users to independently create, navigate, and interpret Google Slides presentations using audio prompts and gesture input. Tagged PDFs, semantic HTML, and accessible authoring environments (such as DAISY and ARIA templates) enabled logical content flow compatible with screen readers.

Where people with disabilities participate in the activities outlined in these research papers, the accessibility of information required to support participation was central to the principle of representation. For example, multiple alternative representations were used to communicate participants' ideas and designs in the DIY- AT Makerspace activities described by Higgins et al. (2025), and these were evaluated as alternative means of representation.

These systems reflect the UDL principle of providing multiple means of representation for diverse learners.

2.10.1.1 Technologies

A variety of technologies were used to support the creation and use of accessible instructional content:

- A11yBoard: A multimodal Chrome extension and iOS app for independently authoring slides using audio feedback, touch interaction, and spatial memory (Zhang et al., 2023).
- Tagged PDFs and Semantic HTML: Designed for screen reader navigation with consistent structure (Archambault, 2011; Pavlíček & Kabelka, 2012; Landra, 2012).
- Authoring platforms such as Subtitle Workshop and Universal Subtitles (Kopeček, Ošlejšek, Plhák, 2012), used to create accessible video/audio content with captions and descriptions.

- Accessible templates for educational presentations, documents, and STEM content using MathML and ARIA attributes (Periša, Peraković, Remenar, 2012).
- DIY Assistive Technology, including finger splints, headbands, pencil grips, tactile maps produced using 3D printing (Higgins et al. 2025).
- Document conversion pipelines, such as ODT to DAISY XML, for structured academic content (Másilko & Pecl, 2013).
- Screen reader-compatible learning management systems, such as Moodle with integrated accessibility plugins (Archambault, 2011).

2.10.1.2 Blind/Low-Vision

While many of these systems were developed with blind users in mind, tools such as screen magnifiers, contrast themes, and adaptive templates (Archambault, 2011; Másilko & Pecl, 2013) also addressed low-vision accessibility. A11yBoard's incompatibility with VoiceOver on iOS was a noted barrier for blind users, but its multimodal design aimed to reduce reliance on sighted peers during content creation (Zhang et al., 2023).

Some studies, such as Higgins et al. (2025), were not specifically focused on blind or low-vision outcomes but involved a blind participant and therefore remain relevant to this review.

2.10.2 Action and Expression

2.10.2.1 Methodology

Zhang et al. (2023) employed a case study approach involving two blind participants using A11yBoard in real-world academic contexts over a one-week period. They collected data through interviews, backend logs, and usage observation.

Several studies presented implementation evaluations of accessible learning management systems and document workflows, often using user testing with screen reader users and educators (Archambault, 2011; Pavlíček & Kabelka, 2012; Onishi & Ono, 2012; Landra, 2012; Kopeček, Ošlejšek, Plhák, 2012; Periša, Peraković, Remenar, 2012). Higgins et al. (2025) examined co-creation through a social justice lens, with the process evaluated through observation and semi-structured interviews.

2.10.2.2 Barriers/Challenges

Major challenges include:

- Incompatibility with common screen readers (e.g., VoiceOver on iOS, NVDA with Google Slides) (Zhang et al., 2023).
- Lack of undo/redo functionality in authoring tools.
- Limited template libraries that meet accessibility standards across diverse content types.
- Instructor dependency, where blind learners rely on sighted peers for formatting or layout-sensitive content (Onishi & Ono, 2012; Periša, Peraković, Remenar, 2012).
- Low adoption of accessibility authoring tools in formal education environments due to training gaps or complexity.
- Lack of familiarity with co-creation processes and associated technologies, including terminology used (Higgins et al., 2025).
- Additional time required to complete tasks (Higgins et al., 2025).

2.10.3 Engagement

2.10.3.1 Pedagogical approach

Pedagogical practices centred on enabling students to engage directly with educational content creation, not just consumption. Tools such as A11yBoard promoted student autonomy by allowing learners to build and review presentations, aligned with constructivist and student-driven learning approaches. Document accessibility initiatives were grounded in universal design, ensuring materials were adaptable, perceivable, and navigable by all students (Landra, 2012; Kopeček, Ošlejšek, Plhák, 2012; Periša, Peraković, Remenar, 2012). Higgins et al. (2025) developed Assistive Technologies through a Makerspace co-creation learning experience in which reflection on the social justice dimensions of the work was encouraged.

2.10.3.2 Support and training

Effective implementation depended on scaffolded training. A11yBoard included cheat sheets, usage tutorials, and gesture command recall features. Several DAISY and ARIA-based systems offered instructor-facing training on best practices for creating accessible formats (Landra, 2012; Másilko & Pecl, 2013). However, gaps remain in widespread teacher professional development and institutional support structures for these technologies.

In some cases, support to address the inexperience of participants was built into the process. For example, Higgins et al. (2025) involved experienced technical staff to support participants with 3D printing.

2.10.4 Summary & Recommendations

When creating accessible studying content, the best practice is to follow established accessibility guidelines, including clear document structure, consistent heading levels, etc. Every non-text element – such as images or text embedded within images – should be accompanied by an alternative format, such as alternative text, captions, or descriptive explanations. Design considerations, including contrast, spacing, and layout, should also be addressed to ensure content is perceivable and navigable.

Accessible templates can significantly support this process by reducing complexity and time demands during content creation. The literature reviewed in this section further highlights the importance of accessible authoring tools and structured workflows to enable learners to independently create and engage with educational materials.

2.11 Summary of UDL Findings

Overall, applying the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework across the reviewed domains shows that most existing work focuses on improving Representation, primarily through technological solutions. In contrast, the principles of Action and Expression, and particularly Engagement, are less consistently and systematically addressed.

Across domains, recurring patterns emerge. Accessibility efforts frequently rely on adapting or supplementing mainstream tools rather than redesigning learning environments from the outset. While many promising prototypes and targeted interventions exist, large-scale implementation and long-term evaluation in Higher Education settings remain limited. In addition, several studies highlight that accessibility is not only a question of tools, but also of pedagogical design, institutional support, and inclusive workflows.

Taken together, the findings suggest that while significant progress has been made in enabling access to content, further work is required to integrate UDL principles more holistically into Computer Science curricula, ensuring that representation, expression, and engagement are addressed in a balanced and sustainable way.

3 Computer Science

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This chapter focuses on how Computer Science (CS) subjects are made more accessible for blind and visually impaired students in Higher Education. CS brings specific challenges for accessibility, because it often involves abstract concepts, visual notations, specialised development tools and fast interaction with complex user interfaces.

The chapter explores how technological innovations have served as key drivers in addressing accessibility challenges and barriers in Computer Science education for blind and visually impaired students in higher education. First, it presents an overview of tools and technologies designed to support the teaching of core CS subjects in higher education, together with the specific challenges these technologies aim to address and their current limitations.

The tools discussed range from image accessibility solutions to screen-reader compatible code navigation. They are relevant for a wide range of CS modules, including programming, web development, networks, mathematics and software engineering, which are standard components of most third-level CS curricula and therefore have high pedagogical and academic relevance.

However, the review finds limited real-world validation of these tools in actual higher-education settings, which points to a gap between research prototypes and everyday practice, as well as a noticeable absence of research on the role of AI in this context. The chapter concludes with high-level recommendations for future work that can support the design of more accessible CS curricula within Access2CS.

The following section presents our findings, organised into core computer science subjects, mathematical and visual domains, applied and technical domains, and cross-cutting assistive technologies. For each subject area, we describe the tools used to support teaching and learning, the reasons behind their development, the challenges they aim to address, and the limitations reported both in our analysis and in the original studies. Tools that span multiple subjects – for example, general assistive technologies or data visualisation and charting tools – are discussed in dedicated cross-cutting subsections.

This section summarises the findings of the review for different areas of Computer Science. It first discusses core CS subjects, followed by mathematical and visual domains, applied and technical domains, and finally cross-cutting assistive technologies that can be used across multiple subjects.

3.1 Core Computer Science Subjects

3.1.1 Programming

3.1.1.1 Code Mirror Block (CMB)

Code Mirror Block (CMB) (Schanzer et al., 2019) is a browser-based, language-independent tool used to address code navigation and code editing challenges posed by visual browser-based tools.

The tool enables students to access the structural representation of source code rather than relying solely on raw text. It generates an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) representation that can be navigated using keyboard shortcuts, thereby supporting non-visual code exploration. In addition, CMB “*decouples the textual syntax from the spoken descriptive label for that text, allowing for plain-language description of fragments of code*” (Schanzer et al., 2019, p. 774).

Limitations

A key limitation relates to real-world validation. Study participants were blind programmers but were not evaluated within a Higher Education setting. Furthermore, although the tool was designed with novice users in mind, participants were “expert” users.

Evaluation

CMB improved users' ability to orient themselves within code as it conveyed structural context rather than relying on line numbers. The tool also enabled faster navigation, as features like collapsible blocks allowed users to skim and skip irrelevant sections efficiently.

3.1.1.2 Grid-Coding

Ehtesham-UI-Haque et al. (2022) propose an editor called **Grid-Coding** aimed at Blind and Low-Vision (BLV) programmers. The editor is primarily intended for use with the Python programming language, although a version that is compatible with Java has also been developed.

The tool is designed to address the difficulty of browsing through source code with a screen reader, which typically assumes a linear reading sequence that is suitable for natural language but not for source code.

To address this, the editor parses code into an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST), which is then presented to the user in the form of a spreadsheet-like “grid”. Indented code blocks are displayed as new columns to the programmer. Audio cues (earons and spearons) provide contextual information to the user.

The editor is modal (i.e., it functions similarly to Vim), with distinct editing and browsing modes. This distinction is intended to support users who perceive browsing and editing as separate tasks, allowing the editor to behave differently depending on the activity.

Cells on the grid can only be edited if it is semantically meaningful to do so. For example, cells that represent an indentation can only be modified if the user explicitly "unindents" a block of code.

Limitations

All study participants reported significant prior programming experience.

Evaluation

The tool was tested with a group of 12 users, who provided very positive feedback regarding its functionality and usability.

3.1.1.3 Quorum

Quorum (Stefik et al., n.d.) is an open-source programming language and environment aimed at disabled users. The system was initially developed for blind programmers, but the project has since expanded in scope. It is a long-term research project that has been in continuous development since 2011.

The language is described as being the world's first "evidence-oriented" language, with significant work being put into testing and validating the language on representative users.

The environment supports both a traditional text-based programming language and a Scratch-like visual syntax designed for younger learners (although the visual syntax is not useful for BLV users).

In terms of structure, the language has a syntax comparable to Lua- or Ruby-like languages. It is statically typed and includes a relatively large standard library supporting activities such as game development and basic data science.

The language is supported by an Integrated Development Environment (IDE) designed to be accessible for screen reader users. The environment also includes documentation and high-quality compiler error feedback, which have been reported as useful for teaching programming to disabled users.

Limitations

Most of the research on Quorum appears to focus on school-age learners rather than university students, which may limit the direct transferability of findings to a Higher Education context.

Although the language is similar to mainstream programming languages and it would probably also be perfectly usable by non-disabled users, learners are still required to learn a language that is not used in industry.

Evaluation

The usability of the language was verified by measuring how long it took novice programmers to complete programming tasks using Quorum vs. other languages.

3.1.1.4 Programming Accessibility: A Literature Review

Mountapmbeme et al. (2022) conducted a literature review on the accessibility challenges faced by Blind and Visually Impaired (BVI) students and professionals in programming. The review identifies key barriers encountered when interacting with programming environments and surveys a range of technological tools developed to address these challenges. It also highlights limitations within the existing research landscape.

The literature review identifies barriers related to programming tools and environments and evaluates a wide array of proposed solutions. These **barriers** include:

- **Code Navigation:** Screen readers typically only allow linear reading, making it difficult for users to track their position within code or to perceive its structural organisation.
- **Code Comprehension:** Users experience loss of contextual information and difficulty interpreting nesting, whitespace, and syntactic layout.
- **Code Debugging:** Most debugging tools rely heavily on visual feedback; real-time cues such as squiggles are not accessible through screen readers.
- **Code Editing:** In-place editing can be error-prone, leading many users to rely on temporary buffers.
- **Code Skimming:** The sequential nature of screen readers limits users' ability to obtain high-level overviews of code.
- **Block-Based Programming:** Environments like Scratch are largely inaccessible due to their mouse-driven design.
- **IDE Accessibility:** Features like tree navigation, tooltips, or watch windows often don't translate to Assistive Technologies.

The literature review catalogues a range of tools designed or adapted to support BVI users in programming environments. These **tools** are grouped into several categories based on their functional approach to accessibility.

- **Screen Reader-Compatible IDE Plugins**
StructJumper, CodeTalk, SODBeans, AudioHighlight, Aural Tree Navigator
- **Audio-Based Programming Tools**
Wicked Audio Debugger, APL (Audio Programming Language), ACONT
- **Accessible Programming Languages**
Quorum, GUIDL, APL, and scripting languages designed for blind users
- **Block-Based and Tangible Programming Tools**
Blocks4All, CodeRhythm, StoryBlocks, Torino, TIP-Toy
- **Assistive Input/Output Mechanisms**
Tactile devices (Tactile Code Skimmer), auditory cues (speech, spearcons, earcons), and keyboard-based navigation
- **Programming Toolkits for Education**
Bonk (audio game development), CodeBox64, and P-CUBE (robotics programming via tactile blocks)

The literature review also documents a number of custom **programming languages** and language-based systems developed specifically with BVI users in mind. These include:

- **Quorum** – A fully accessible, evidence-based language supported by its own accessible IDE and widely used in schools.
- **APL (Audio Programming Language)** – A voice-command-based environment for writing and debugging code using audio interaction alone.
- **GUIDL** – A natural-language-like code for describing graphical user interfaces (GUIs), intended to support blind programmers.
- **Pseudospacial Blocks** – A non-visual representation of block-based programming that uses keyboard input and speech output to convey structural relationships.
- **Scripting Language** (Siegfried et al.) – A text-based scripting alternative to inaccessible GUI builders such as Visual Basic.

Similar to the findings of this report, Mountapmbeme et al. (2022) identified **limitations** in the analysed literature:

- **Understudied Areas:** Certain aspects of programming accessibility, such as code editing and debugging, remain relatively underexplored.
- **Scope of Studies:** Many studies focus on specific tools or prototype rather than examining the overall educational contexts.
- **Real-World Validation:** Several tools are only evaluated through small-scale user studies or pilot tests, meaning scalability and long-term impact remain largely unproven.
- **Limited Higher Education Focus:** While higher education is covered, many tools are designed for kindergarten through 12th grade (K-12) contexts, making transferability to university-level Computer Science less direct.
- **Lack of Longitudinal Data:** Few studies assess sustained educational outcomes or transitions from assistive learning tools into professional programming environments.

Limitations

We refer the reader to the original paper for details regarding the review methodology, including search scope, inclusion criteria, and database coverage.

Evaluation

The review provides a structured synthesis of accessibility challenges faced by blind and visually impaired individuals in programming. It catalogues a wide range of assistive technologies, programming environments, and educational tools, and organises barriers into thematic categories such as navigation, debugging, and code comprehension. By consolidating findings across multiple studies, the review offers a useful overview of the current state of programming accessibility research and highlights areas requiring further development.

3.1.1.5 Educational Experiences of Blind Programmers: A Qualitative Study

Baker et al. (2019) investigates the **educational experiences** of blind Computer Science (CS) students in Higher Education. Through surveys with 15 blind male programmers and follow-up interviews with 10 participants, the study explores the barriers they encountered, the accommodations provided, and how these factors shaped their academic experiences. The study was performed in 2019 and the participants were programmers who had already completed a degree in CS or related fields. The research highlights the pervasive nature of inaccessibility, from IDEs and course materials to social interactions and assessments, and suggests actionable improvements across institutional, technological, and pedagogical domains.

Four mainstream IDEs – Visual Studio, Eclipse, Notepad, and Notepad++ – were most commonly used despite their partial accessibility. The participants used the following screen readers: JAWS (most commonly used), NVDA, Window Eyes, and VoiceOver. Braille displays were used by some. Learning tools such as Learning Ally (for audiobooks), Optical Character Recognition (OCR) software, and tactile diagrams were also used.

Participants reported having alternative forms of assignments, for example console-based projects instead of GUI-based. The use of readers or sighted partners to describe or interact with visual content was also reported. Diagrams were made available either in tactile form or with oral or written descriptions, with varied effectiveness. Course materials were sometimes substituted or entirely omitted due to accessibility challenges.

Limitations

The study involved a relatively small participant group consisting of 15 blind male programmers, with follow-up interviews conducted with 10 participants.

As participants had already completed their degrees, the findings are based on retrospective accounts of their educational experiences.

Evaluation

Many accommodations were inconsistent, improvised, and often inadequate due to a lack of faculty training and accessible materials. Disability service offices offered textbook transcription and alternative formats, but with varying success.

The study participants reported having difficulties with inaccessible features in IDEs (e.g., debuggers, interface builders, syntax highlighting), inability to install necessary Assistive Technologies on institutional computers, and poor Optical Character Recognition (OCR) results when scanning code-heavy textbooks.

Communication challenges were also identified. Lectures often excluded verbal descriptions of visual content, and misunderstandings occurred during oral exams or group work due to a lack of shared visual references. The participants additionally reported social challenges, including isolation resulting from inaccessible group projects and broader social exclusion.

3.1.1.6 Summary and Recommendations

BVI students face a range of barriers when learning and practising programming. Many mainstream IDEs remain only partially accessible, and the structure of programming languages themselves can introduce additional challenges.

For example, most programming languages frequently rely on nested structures, that are visually represented through indentation and spatial layout, which are straightforward for sighted users to interpret. For BVI individuals, however, it is not always evident whether they are operating within a function or control structure, as this information must be sequentially

read and cognitively retained. As a result, code containing multiple nested functions or conditional statements can be particularly difficult to comprehend. In languages such as Python, where indentation carries syntactic meaning, these structural accessibility challenges are further intensified.

Debugging, navigating between sections, and scanning code for specific elements were also identified as significant challenges within the reviewed literature.

A range of specialised programming solutions have been developed to address these accessibility barriers, including accessible programming languages such as Quorum (Stefik et al., n.d.), structural navigation tools such as Code Mirror Block (Schanzer et al., 2019), and alternative programming environments designed to support non-visual code interaction.

Beyond the solutions identified in the reviewed literature, community-developed add-ons for screen readers such as NVDA and JAWS have been created to improve accessibility within mainstream environments such as Visual Studio Code. While these environments are not fully accessible, such extensions can make them more usable in comparison to their default configurations. This may allow BVI students to work with the same programming languages and platforms as their peers, thereby supporting participation in collaborative contexts, such as team-based projects, where shared tools are beneficial.

3.1.1.7 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Code Mirror Block (CMB) - A structural code navigation and representation tool that supports non-visual exploration of programming constructs and nested code structures.
- Quorum - An accessible programming language and integrated development environment designed to support blind and visually impaired users through screen reader compatibility and structured syntax.
- Screen Reader Mode Extensions for Visual Studio Code - Beyond the solutions identified in the reviewed literature, community-developed add-ons for screen readers such as NVDA and JAWS have been created to improve accessibility within mainstream environments such as Visual Studio Code.

3.1.2 Software Engineering

3.1.2.1 Adapting a Systems Analysis and Design Course for a Blind Student

Carruthers et al. (2023) describes the process of adapting a **Systems Analysis and Design course** for a blind student at a university. The course made extensive use of Unified Modeling Language (UML diagrams), which needed to be made accessible to the student

To address this, PlantUML was selected as the diagramming tool, as it stores diagrams in a text-based format that can be opened and edited in a standard text editor. This enabled the blind student to collaborate with sighted classmates. Some sighted students also reported that editing diagrams as text was useful and better suited their learning style. The blind student's diagrams could be evaluated in the same way as those of sighted students, supporting fairness in assessment and reducing perceptions of unequal advantage.

Limitations

A major limitation of the study is that it describes the experience of a single student enrolled in a single subject at one university. As such, the findings are context-specific and may not be generalisable to other institutions or courses.

Evaluation

The adoption of a text-based diagramming approach facilitated collaborative work between blind and sighted students and enabled consistent evaluation of submitted work. The approach also demonstrated that accessible design choices can benefit a broader range of learners, not only those with visual impairments.

3.1.2.2 Accessible UML Diagram Representation for Blind Students

Müller (2012) presents a very short paper describing how **UML diagrams** were communicated to blind students undertaking Computer Science and Software Engineering courses at a university.

Two primary approaches are proposed: tactile diagrams and text-based representations. The author recommends using both modalities to maximise student comprehension.

Tactile diagrams were produced by converting the UML diagrams provided to sighted students into embossed tactile formats printed on specialised paper. These diagrams were created using a tactile printer, which is a relatively expensive piece of equipment.

Different text representations were provided depending on the type of diagram. For example, class diagrams were presented in tabular form, which is notable given that screen readers can experience difficulties when interpreting tables.

PlantUML is also identified as a suitable alternative, along with similar tools that allow text input to be converted into diagrams. The website WebSequencing is additionally mentioned.

Limitations

It is unclear how many students were involved in the implementation or how effective the proposed approaches were in practice.

Evaluation

Two accessible representation approaches – tactile and text-based – are proposed, with the author recommending their combined use to support student comprehension. However, it remains unclear how effective the process was in practice.

3.1.2.3 Py2UML

Py2UML is a web-based tool designed to help BVI students create UML class diagrams just by writing Python code (Verde et al., 2023). The tool was developed in response to the limited accessibility of traditional UML diagramming environments, which often do not function effectively with screen readers such as NVDA, particularly when interpreting visual elements such as shapes, connectors, and menus.

Py2UML converts Python code into UML class diagrams and is designed to be fully usable by visually impaired users through screen reader interaction, with the aim of making UML learning more inclusive within Computer Science education.

Limitations

The evidence base for effectiveness is limited due to the very small scale of testing and the early stage of the tool.

Evaluation

Real-world validation is currently limited: the tool has only been tested by one participant and is in the early stages of development (Verde et al., 2023).

3.1.2.4 Summary and Recommendations:

Accessible diagrams represent one of the primary challenges when teaching Software Engineering. In most teaching materials, diagrams are provided only as images (e.g., PNG or JPG formats), that do not contain information that screen readers can interpret.

When expressing class structures of a systems architecture, accessible UML diagrams are needed. PlantUML provides an effective approach, as diagrams can be both created and viewed textually. This multimodal representation allows content to be accessed through screen readers while also supporting diagram creation. As a result, blind students are able both to explore and produce UML diagrams. PlantUML is actively maintained and freely available, supporting its adoption in educational contexts.

A textual alternative to visually complex diagrams can also help other students in the classroom to understand them – broader accessibility benefits all learners. In addition, Py2UML allows the export of Python programs into PlantUML, providing a quick way to generate documentation.

3.1.2.5 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Py2UML - Converts Python code in PlantUML graphs
- PlantUML - text based graphing Tool
- Svgs with Embedded Information

3.1.3 Web development

3.1.3.1 TangibleGrid

TangibleGrid (Li et al., 2022) is a hardware device proposed to allow blind web developers to prototype web page layouts without needing assistance from sighted people. It is based on the observation that blind web developers often find page layout design to be one of the most challenging aspect of web development and frequently require support from sighted peers.

Users place telescopically extendable frames (representing elements of a web page such as frames or images) onto a physical board. Electronics embedded in the board detect the placement of these frames and transmit the information to software on a computer, which automatically generates the corresponding CSS and HTML required to implement the layout.

Limitations

The system requires specialised hardware and software, which may necessitate significant accommodations from teaching staff and institutions. It is also unlikely to be useful to sighted users in its current form.

In addition, the system can only support relatively simple layouts, limiting its applicability for more complex web design tasks.

Evaluation

The system enables blind users to independently prototype and explore web layouts through tactile interaction. It demonstrates an alternative, non-visual approach to layout design that translates physical configurations into functional web code.

The approach may also have applications beyond web development, such as supporting the layout design of presentation slides or other spatial digital artefacts.

3.1.3.2 Teaching Web Development to Screen Reader Users

Ferrari et al. (2023) propose a **web development course** aimed at screen reader users, covering the fundamentals of HTML, CSS and JavaScript.

The course was delivered to a group of 12 students from varied backgrounds. These participants were not college students (average age 39), though all had previously completed Higher Education, with nearly half holding Master's degrees. The course made use of a dedicated website, online lectures, and Teaching Assistants (TA) support meetings.

The course covered topics that are presumed to be challenging to a blind user including fonts, colours, and layout/styling. The following adaptations were implemented for each topic:

- Fonts were taught using embossed font samples accompanied by Braille descriptions.
- Colour theory was taught through an embossed colour wheel labelled in Braille, with embossed lines allowing students to trace complementary colour relationships.
- Layouts and CSS styling were taught using embossed website representations, both with and without CSS enabled, again labelled in Braille.

Limitations

The course was delivered to a small cohort of 12 participants who were not current Higher Education students, limiting direct transferability to traditional university classroom settings.

Evaluation

The authors report that preparing accessible lecture materials required a significant time investment. Recruiting suitable TAs also proved challenging.

Students generally found the HTML unit easy to understand, whereas the CSS and JavaScript units were reported as substantially more difficult. Difficulty with CSS appeared to depend on students' prior familiarity with designing layouts for sighted users. Most students found the JavaScript unit challenging, which may reflect limited prior exposure to programming concepts.

Students also reported that TAs were often unfamiliar with screen readers, making it difficult for them to provide effective support.

3.1.3.3 Blind Web Development Training

Ferrari et al. (2019) describes the work involved in developing and evaluating a seven-day **web development course**. The course was taught to 13 blind and low-vision students who had no prior experience building websites.

JAWS was the primary screen reader used for navigating and writing code. Students used text-based editors (e.g., Notepad++) to write HTML and CSS. A custom Color Namer tool

provided named colour feedback for RGB values. Tactile graphics were also used, including raised-dot diagrams such as tactile versions of Google's layout.

Limitations

Real-world validation is limited, as the course was delivered in a technology camp rather than a college setting. The average age of participants was 24, ranging from 18 to 35 years.

Tactile diagrams were often unfamiliar and difficult to interpret, especially for those without prior exposure to tactile graphics or when diagrams lacked clear outlines.

Time was insufficient to adequately cover core topics such as HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. The authors suggest that either the duration of the course should be increased or the learning objectives should be scaled back. The course progressed more slowly than expected due to varying levels of screen reader proficiency and technical obstacles.

Evaluation

Participants acquired foundational web development skills and self-reported a strong sense of pride and enthusiasm to continue their studies following the program. Responses varied based on students' visual ability.

3.1.3.4 Summary and Recommendations:

Ferrari et al. (2019) demonstrate that it is possible to teach students the fundamentals of web development to BLV students when sufficient instructional support and time are provided. HTML was generally reported as manageable, as it is a language that produces static output, whereas JavaScript presented greater challenges for students, likely due to its increased complexity compared to HTML, particularly for those without a programming background.

Some research has focused on making the visual aspects of web development, such as layout and design, accessible to blind learners (Ferrari et al., 2023). However, extending these approaches to concepts such as colour presents additional challenges. Teaching colour solely through colour theory may not fully convey the experiential dimensions typically associated with its use in design – an analogy would be attempting to teach music to deaf individuals solely through written notation.

Approaches that translate visual layouts into tangible or spatial representations, such as TangibleGrid (Li et al., 2022), offer a promising means of including blind users in visual design. Furthermore, as documented by Ferrari et al. (2019), tactile models can be incorporated to support the teaching of CSS, a language that students reported finding particularly challenging.

3.1.3.5 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Screen readers like NVDA or Jaws

- TangibleGrid (or something else)
- Tactile Models

3.1.4 Data Structures

3.1.4.1 Improving Understanding of Data Structures with Tactile Media

Crockett and Gannod (2020) describe a **multimodal approach to teaching Data Structures** using spoken explanations, tactile diagrams, and code examples. A combination of tools was used, including tactile diagrams created with Microsoft Visio, Braille fonts, swell paper printed with a tactile printer, and a Universal User-Centered Design approach incorporating multiple teaching supports such as accessible textbooks (Zybooks), JAWS screen readers, MathType, and EquatIO.

The authors developed a structured design process for the development of their tools consisting of Design, Feedback, Iteration, Construction, and Printing. Diagrams were first created in Microsoft Visio and then translated into Braille using the Braille Kiama TrueType font. The tactile materials covered topics including linked lists, trees, graphs, heaps, and queues. Animations were broken into sequences of tactile diagrams. Higher Education students provided continuous feedback, which was used to refine the diagrams and improve clarity, readability, and pedagogical effectiveness.

Limitations

The approach has several practical limitations. It requires specialised hardware, including tactile printers and swell paper. The preparation of tactile diagrams is labour-intensive, as diagrams must be designed, tested, and printed. Scalability is also constrained by physical size limitations (e.g., 8.5 × 11 inches paper), which restrict the complexity that can be represented in a single diagram.

Evaluation

Tactile diagrams significantly improved comprehension of abstract data structures for blind students. Students reported an increased ability to conceptualize topics such as linked lists, AVL trees, and flowcharts.

3.1.4.2 GSK (Graph SKetching)

Balik et al. (2013) introduce **GSK (Graph SKetching)**, a universally accessible tool designed to enable both blind and sighted users to create, edit, and share combinatorial graphs in real-time. Recognizing the pivotal role of node-link diagrams in computer science and the challenges they pose for blind students, GSK offers an interface compatible with standard interaction mechanisms, including screen readers. The tool was effectively utilized by a blind

Computer Science student and instructors in graph-intensive courses, such as automata theory and operating systems.

By adhering to universal design principles, GSK facilitates collaborative learning and aims to bridge the accessibility gap in STEM education. The authors developed GSK as a tool that allows for the creation and manipulation of node-link diagrams using standard input methods (keyboard and mouse) while remaining compatible with screen readers. GSK is developed to be inherently accessible, ensuring that both blind and sighted users can operate within the same interface without the need for specialized hardware or software. GSK is a Java application built using standard Swing components that leverages the Java Accessibility API. It was developed and tested on a Windows platform using the JAWS screen reader.

By enabling blind students to create and share graphs, GSK fosters an inclusive learning environment where all students can participate equally in graph-related assignments and discussions.

Limitations

Controlled, large-scale user studies were not conducted to determine how intuitive the interface and paradigm are, or to what extent GSK provides blind and sighted users with computationally equivalent access to graphs.

In addition, this work was primarily focused on blind users, while the needs of low-vision users were not explicitly addressed.

Evaluation

The tool was integrated into real coursework, demonstrating its applicability in real-world educational settings.

The tool was integrated into real coursework contexts, demonstrating applicability in educational settings. One blind computer science student used GSK to complete assignments and participate in class activities involving graph creation and interpretation. Observations of the student's interactions were collected, alongside instructor feedback regarding performance and engagement.

GSK was assessed in terms of its effectiveness in supporting graph comprehension and production, as well as its impact on participation alongside sighted peers. The tool is reported to be simple and straightforward, with perceived usability for blind and sighted students as well as teaching staff.

3.1.4.3 Summary and Recommendations

Tactile representations of graphs are a highly effective medium for making complex data structures accessible to individuals who cannot rely on visual input. However, they require significant time and effort to design, produce, and distribute.

Tools such as Graph SKetching (Balik et al., 2013) enable both sighted and blind users to create and manipulate accessible graphs by providing a secondary, textual mode of interaction. More broadly, textual descriptions can serve as a supplement to visual representations, supporting access to graph-based content beyond tool-specific environments.

3.1.4.4 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Physical Graphs of Data Structures
- Graph Sketching
- Textual Descriptions (alt text)

3.2 Mathematics and Visual Domains

3.2.1 Mathematics

3.2.1.1 SZS

SZS (Melfi et al., 2018) is an open-source LaTeX editor designed for BLV users. While Braille is commonly used to read mathematical formulae, the authors argue that it is inadequate due to the existence of multiple competing Braille mathematics notations, none of which are widely used.

LaTeX is proposed to be a more effective alternative for mathematical notation, as it is widely used, accessible to both sighted and blind users, and provides students with a transferable academic and professional skill.

SZS was developed to be highly compatible with screen readers. This was achieved by hiding the LaTeX header by default, implementing effective go-to-line and autocomplete functionality, and abridging compiler output to improve readability through screen readers. Code folding is also supported, addressing non-linear navigation challenges similar to those found in source code environments. In addition, a focus manager was implemented to ensure that interface focus changes occur in an intuitive manner for screen reader users.

Limitations

The learning curve associated with LaTeX is relatively high, although this challenge is not unique to blind students and is also experienced by sighted learners. The system was tested on only three students, limiting the breadth of evaluation.

Evaluation

Given that the tool was evaluated with only three participants, it is difficult to draw strong conclusions regarding its overall effectiveness or generalisability.

3.2.1.2 Boot Strap Algebra: WeScheme IDE

Bootstrap: Algebra uses the **WeScheme IDE**, a browser-based programming environment, to teach algebra through image-based programming (Schanzer et al., 2020). The environment has been adapted to make geometric image creation accessible to blind and visually impaired students by supporting screen readers and keyboard navigation.

The WeScheme IDE provides several accessibility features, including scene graph descriptions and annotations for generated shapes, colour naming based on the Lab colour space, AI-generated descriptions of web images, accessible animation feedback, an accessible IDE interface, structure-aware code navigation, and error-tolerant programming. The environment is also used for visual programming with Racket.

Limitations

Schanzer et al. (2020) testing of WeScheme was conducted with secondary level students (aged 12-16) rather than Higher Education students, limiting direct transferability to university contexts.

Students were not familiar with screen readers, and the researchers had assumed that many would already be comfortable with basic keyboard shortcuts and spoken feedback. The authors recommend that classroom time should be allocated to developing these foundational skills.

The tool supports only one specific element of algebra: composition.

Evaluation

All students successfully used WeScheme to write simple image-generating programs in Racket and overwhelmingly preferred text-based programming for short expressions. Many reported programming as their favourite activity of the day.

3.2.1.3 Theorem Prover-Based Inclusive Mathematical Learning Environment

Stöger et al. (2022) propose a system that uses a **theorem prover** to assist blind and low-vision users with their maths education. The system remains conceptual and has not yet been implemented.

The theorem prover would provide students with hints on how to proceed as they work on a problem within a text editor. The system builds on an earlier platform aimed at sighted users called ISAC. While ISAC used the jEdit editor, the proposed system transitions to Visual

Studio Code, which is considered substantially more accessible due to its Electron/Chromium framework and compatibility with screen readers. The system would use a LaTeX-like notation for mathematical expression.

Limitations

The system is currently only a proposal and has not yet been implemented or tested in practice. In addition, the use of LaTeX-like notation may present a steep learning curve for students.

Evaluation

As the system has not yet been implemented, its effectiveness in supporting mathematical learning for blind and low-vision students cannot currently be evaluated. The authors note that such a system could also benefit sighted students, as it actively supports learners by providing step-by-step instructional guidance.

3.2.1.4 Simplified LaTeX-Based Notation for Blind Students

Jencic (2012) presents a **simplified LaTeX-based** mathematical notation system designed for blind students participating in mainstream education. The notation is based on LaTeX but simplified to improve usability on Braille displays.

The approach discourages the use of general text-formatting commands in LaTeX, instead recommending that LaTeX be used primarily for mathematical expressions. It also tightens spacing conventions within standard LaTeX to optimise readability on Braille displays. In addition, the author provides macros that allow this notation to be used within Microsoft Word.

The notation system is the outcome of a project initiated by a research group in Slovenia in 2006.

Limitations

Documents produced using this notation may appear visually poor to sighted readers, which presents challenges when materials are intended to be shared between blind and sighted users. Furthermore, the Braille-oriented notation is not directly usable by sighted users.

Evaluation

The work focuses on the design and presentation of the notation rather than on empirical assessment of its effectiveness in educational practice.

3.2.1.5 Designing Auditory Cues to Enhance Spoken Mathematics

Murphy et al. (2010) address the difficulty of presenting mathematical content in a form that is accessible to blind students, arguing that a purely speech-based modality is insufficient.

The paper proposes supplementing speech output with non-verbal **auditory cues**, such as earcons and spearcons. This approach builds on prior work in auditory mathematics representation, which often required users to learn complex grammars or possess musical knowledge in order to interpret audio cues effectively. The proposed system seeks to avoid these requirements.

The approach aims to provide blind and low-vision users with a deeper understanding of the structural relationships within mathematical formulae presented through audio.

Limitations

The work focuses specifically on auditory augmentation of spoken mathematics and does not address multimodal alternatives.

Evaluation

The approach aims to provide blind and low-vision users with a deeper understanding of the structural relationships within mathematical formulae presented through audio.

3.2.1.6 Multisensual Access to Formulas with Braille Converters

Mikulowski (2022) presents software to allow automatic conversion between maths representations. For example, formulae written in MathML by sighted users can be **automatically converted into Braille** representations familiar to blind users, and vice versa. This functionality is particularly relevant in educational contexts where blind students are often taught by sighted teaching staff.

The conversion process is supported by the open-source Liblouis Braille library. The software is available both as a Windows desktop application and as a web application. Development followed a needs analysis conducted with 142 respondents and was carried out across two projects spanning three countries.

In addition to conversion between representations, the system allows for the editing and viewing of formulae and includes functionality for sonifying function graphs.

Limitations

Some of the technologies used to implement the system appear to be discontinued, which may affect long-term sustainability and maintenance.

Evaluation

The system was developed following a needs analysis involving 142 respondents, indicating that its design was informed by user requirements.

3.2.1.7 Accessible LaTeX-based Mathematical Document Authoring and Presentation (ALAP)

Manzoor et al. (2019) introduce **ALAP (Accessible LaTeX-based Mathematical Document Authoring and Presentation)**, a LaTeX editor designed for blind and low-vision users.

The system is self-voicing, meaning it includes built-in text-to-speech functionality and does not rely on external screen readers. It supports the compilation of LaTeX documents into PDF outputs designed to be accessible to screen reader users.

Limitations

Debugging LaTeX code remains a challenge for BLV users, including within the ALAP environment.

Evaluation

The system was extensively compared with TeXclipse, a popular LaTeX editor based on the Eclipse IDE. 18 participants tested the tool and reported ALAP to be more usable than the comparison system.

3.2.1.8 Evaluating Accessible Processing and Presentation of Mathematical Formulae

Ribera et al. (2013) present a comparative evaluation of **mathematical formulae** processed using various mathematical editors, examining their accessibility for blind and visually impaired users.

The study compares formula processing and presentation across multiple software environments to assess how effectively mathematical content can be viewed and interpreted.

Limitations

As the paper dates from 2013, the software tools evaluated – including Microsoft Word 2007, MathType 6.0c, and LibreOffice Math 3.3.2 – are now outdated. This limits the contemporary applicability of the findings.

Evaluation

The paper provides a comparative perspective on the accessibility of mathematical editors available at the time of publication, highlighting differences in how formulae could be processed and presented for blind and visually impaired users.

3.2.1.9 Adapting Mathematical Algorithms for Blind Students

Masilko and Pecl (2013) present adaptations of two standard mathematical algorithms — **polynomial division and matrix multiplication** – for blind students. The methods employed

tools such as the Lambda Math Editor, Excel spreadsheets, simple text editors, and Braille embossing.

The findings indicated that the tactile Braille print was most effective for beginners, helping students grasp matrix structure and spatial layout. The Lambda Math Editor was particularly useful for complex mathematical expressions, as it supports both screen readers and Braille output, unlike standard spreadsheets.

Limitations

The paper focuses on two specific algorithms and represents an initial step rather than a comprehensive framework for accessible mathematical instruction. As such, it addresses only a limited portion of the broader challenges associated with making mathematical algorithms accessible.

Evaluation

The study provides a practical exploration of adapting commonly taught mathematical procedures for blind students and identifies specific tools that support spatial and structural understanding in mathematics education.

3.2.1.10 `latex2nemeth`: A Direct LaTeX-to-Braille Transcribing Method

Papasalouros and Tsolomitis (2015) present a software tool called **latex2nemeth**, which automatically transcribes LaTeX source documents into Nemeth Braille, a code used by blind individuals for reading mathematics. The tool addresses the lack of reliable solutions capable of directly converting LaTeX – the dominant language for mathematical documentation – into accessible Braille formats. It extends the Nemeth code to support more than 800 LaTeX mathematical symbols and produces outputs compatible with embossers and refreshable Braille displays.

`latex2nemeth` is a Java-based command-line application that parses LaTeX documents and generates Braille files in UTF-16 or PEF format. The parser is built using JavaCC and separates LaTeX text and mathematical modes, generating abstract syntax trees for mathematical expressions which are then converted into Nemeth Braille. The system proposes Nemeth extensions to encode previously unsupported LaTeX symbols.

The software supports complex mathematical structures such as fractions, indices, roots, arrays, and operators, and accommodates both Greek and English text modes. A modular architecture allows for backend expansion (e.g., MathSpeak integration). The authors also report developing a repository of Braille-translated mathematics textbooks to broaden access. A full Real Analysis textbook was successfully transcribed using the tool and studied by a blind student in a Greek university mathematics course.

Limitations

The study focuses exclusively on blind users and Nemeth Braille, without addressing the needs of low-vision users. Although the tool was evaluated within a Higher Education context, the user study involved only one blind participant.

Evaluation

The authors compared latex2nemeth against Duxbury and liblouis using representative LaTeX documents from the AMSMath package. latex2nemeth had near-perfect fidelity (only minor issues with ambiguous dot characters), whereas comparison tools produced substantially higher error counts (50+ errors).

A case study was also conducted in which a full Real Analysis textbook was transcribed and used by a blind student in a university mathematics course. A structured interview addressed comprehension, usability, confidence, and workload impact. Findings indicated improved access to course material and reduced reliance on manual transcription or intermediaries, supporting parity with sighted peers.

Qualitative evaluation included student self-report measures of learning impact and satisfaction, alongside informal expert review involving a university mathematics professor and a specialist in mathematics education for visually impaired students. Quantitative performance outcomes (e.g., grades) were not measured.

3.2.1.11 Summary and Recommendations

Teaching mathematics remains challenging within accessible learning contexts. The field is broad, and different subdomains require different accessibility approaches. For example, geometry – due to its inherently visual nature – requires alternative supports compared to areas focused on symbolic or equation-based mathematics.

Bootstrap: Algebra provides feedback when students work with geometric shapes through scene graph descriptions. Instead of relying on visual positioning, the system communicates spatial information through text-to-speech (e.g., describing shape type, dimensions, and rotation). For equation-based work, tools such as SZS provide accessible LaTeX editing environments that allow students to write mathematical expressions in a structured and screen reader-compatible format. Converters that translate LaTeX into Braille, such as TeX-to-Braille systems, further support access to complex mathematical notation. While platforms such as GeoGebra claim accessibility, practical limitations remain, particularly in providing meaningful feedback on drawn functions.

3.2.1.12 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Boot Strap Algebra
- SZS

3.2.2 Data Visualisation

3.2.2.1 Audio-Tactile Reader (ATR)

The authors of Melfi et al. (2022) introduce the **Audio-Tactile Reader (ATR)**, an assistive system for blind Higher Education students that enables interactive exploration of complex and graphical STEM content using a 2D haptic device called Hyper Braille. Unlike traditional tactile paper graphics, ATR allows zooming, semantic filtering (e.g., by colour), and direct interaction with original PDF documents, offering dynamic control and autonomy in understanding graphical educational content. The system was tested with 4 blind STEM students, who found it functional, usable, and largely preferred it over existing embossed paper methods. The study highlights ATR's potential to increase accessibility, autonomy, and comprehension of graphical information in university-level STEM education.

The study centres on the development and evaluation of the ATR system as a technological intervention. The solution includes:

- An HyperBraille S haptic device featuring a two-dimensional pin-matrix tactile display with multi-touch input.
- ATR Software that parses PDF STEM documents into tactile formats, with support for zooming, colour/semantic filtering, screen-reader integration for text, and tactile simplification of complex graphics.

The developed ATR system incorporates the following methods:

- Interactive tactile exploration instead of passive text descriptions.
- Self-directed learning through direct access to standard educational PDFs.
- Independent analysis of real lecture materials without relying on pre-modified, static formats.

Limitations

Several limitations were identified in both the system and the study:

- Previous technologies like IVEO or tactile paper + screen reader setups served as baselines but lacked interactive feedback and autonomy. Limited but emerging use of pin-matrix devices, although often not tested in Higher Education or STEM contexts.
- The main limitations of the ATR system were reported to be connected with the tactile display, such as the device's response time, the accidental triggering of the reading out of text fields via a double tap, and the resolution of the HyperBraille.
- Although the developed system was tested with real educational materials for blind university students, a major limitation of the study is the number of participants

involved in the evaluation. The authors mention the following reasons: the study needed to be conducted on-site in the lab due to the hardware and software required, and it was difficult to find individuals with blindness who are studying STEM subjects in higher education, especially during the pandemic.

- Due to the small number of participants who evaluated the system, it was not possible to determine whether the differences between the compared systems were statistically significant

Evaluation

The authors identified the following limitations of existing Assistive Technologies:

- Tactile paper graphics are static, expensive, labour-intensive, and inflexible to change.
- Rendering STEM visuals in Braille or tactile formats introduces complexity since the layout of the document needs to be modified due to the size of the Braille fonts.
- Semantic information, like colours or details in complex graphs, is difficult to assess.
- Textual descriptions are often insufficient, limiting students' independent comprehension.
- There is a lack of dynamic interaction (e.g., no zoom or filtering) with existing methods.

The authors performed a comparison-based usability study including 4 blind STEM participants (all male, either students or had completed studies), aged 22–51. All participants were frequent users of computers and touch-controlled devices (such as a smartphones), regular users of screen readers (NVDA or JAWS), and had experience with tactile materials. The small sample size was due to the lab-based equipment requirements.

The ATR system was tested and compared with commonly used tactile paper graphics. Each participant in the study explored three documents and answered two questions for each document by using the novel ATR system and a baseline system. As a baseline system, they used a tactile paper + screen reader system (tactile graphics embossed on a paper accompanied by a text document containing a textual description that is read by a screen reader). The study was divided into three phases: (1) interview and familiarisation, (2) testing different document types, and (3) comparing ATR with embossed tactile graphics plus textual description.

The authors conclude that the developed tool is comparable to the baseline system and potentially better, and both its features (colour filters and zoom) were positively evaluated. According to the SUS questionnaire, the system was evaluated as usable and satisfactory (mean score 79). Three out of four participants expressed a preference for the ATR. The given reasons were: the possibility of using filters, and the greater simplicity in perceiving the

tactile elements (greater contrast). The fourth participant preferred the existing method due to long-term familiarity.

3.2.2.2 Producing Accessible Statistics Diagrams in R

Fitzpatrick et al. (2017) propose a solution for the semantic enrichment of graph visualisations (such as bar charts, box plots, and time series). Descriptive graph metadata that semantically explains their contents is embedded within SVG files to convey meaningful information to screen readers. Interactive exploration of the graphs is enabled by utilizing the JavaScript library DIAGcess. Consequently, the users can navigate through different components of a diagram. The authors further ensure integration with other Assistive Technologies like screen readers by making the produced SVG files web accessible. These solutions aim to transform traditional visualisations into accessible formats, empowering blind students to engage with statistical content effectively.

This paper also introduces a method for generating accessible statistical diagrams using the R programming language.

The solution includes the following components:

- The R programming language is utilised for statistical analysis and generating visualisations. The gridSVG package is used for converting R graphics into SVG format, allowing for the inclusion of semantic metadata.
- The DIAGcess JavaScript library is used to enhance SVG files with interactivity, enabling screen readers to interpret and navigate the diagrams in any browser.
- The generated SVG files are thus web accessible, supporting screen reading and interactive exploration.

These tools allow blind users to independently access and understand statistical graphics, enabling both students and professionals' greater possibilities to equally participate in both education and employment.

Evaluation

The evaluation of the proposed solution is limited. Although two of the authors were blind, they did not perform any evaluation of the developed tool.

Limitations

The authors identified several limitations in current visualisation practices:

- Inaccessibility of traditional graphics, as standard statistical diagrams are often not interpretable by screen readers, posing challenges for blind users.

- Lack of semantic information, where visualisations without embedded metadata lack the necessary context for non-visual interpretation.
- Limited interactivity, since static images do not allow blind users to explore data dynamically.

The study is also limited by the lack of evaluation. No user studies were conducted to test the tool or to evaluate it in classroom settings.

3.2.2.3 Data Visualisations on the Web for Screen Reader Users

The study (Fan et al., 2023) investigates the accessibility of web-based data visualisations for BVI users, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the researchers conducted an accessibility audit of 87 visualisations, a survey of 127 screen reader users, and contextual inquiries with 12 users. Their findings show a pervasive lack of accessible design in widely used visualisations and underscore the challenges BVI users face in navigating, interpreting, and gaining insights from online data. The paper concludes with practical recommendations to improve data literacy, user autonomy, and inclusive web practices.

This study is a timely and critical examination of how web-based data visualisations fail to meet the accessibility needs of blind and visually impaired users. While not directly situated in the context of computer science education, the findings have strong implications for data literacy, a core component of CS curricula. The emphasis on multimodal access, semantically rich web design, and user-centric interaction design makes this research relevant for educators, developers, and accessibility advocates.

The identified technologies discussed in the study include:

- Screen readers: NVDA, JAWS, VoiceOver.
- Data sonification tools: SAS Graphics Accelerator, iSonic.
- Web accessibility frameworks: WCAG, Chartability heuristics.
- Multimodal platforms: Born Accessible sites offering summaries, tables, sonification, and dynamic content alternatives.

Evaluation

The paper employed a mixed-methods approach consisting of three complementary studies:

Accessibility Audit

- Sample: 87 online data visualisations (76 from “Top Results” sites, 11 from “Born Accessible” sites).

- Auditors: 3 certified accessibility specialists (2 sighted, 1 blind), with different screen reader and browser combinations.
- Tool: A modified version of the Chartability accessibility heuristics, with 26 criteria organized under four categories: content, context, navigation, and interactivity.
- Process: Visualisations were assessed using screen readers (JAWS, NVDA, VoiceOver) to determine the presence and quality of accessibility features. A Likert scale rated overall accessibility.

Online Survey

- Participants: 127 screen reader users.
- Focus: Collected both quantitative and qualitative data about user experiences, preferences, and strategies in accessing online data, especially COVID-related.
- Outcome: Insights into general challenges, coping mechanisms, and demand for features like sonification or structured tables.

Contextual Inquiry

- Participants: 12 screen reader users from the survey pool.
- Method: Remote observational study where participants navigated visualisations in real time.
- Goal: Explore how "accessible" data representations are used to gain insights.
- Insight: Revealed nuanced gaps between technical accessibility (e.g., WCAG compliance) and practical usability.

The findings of the study include:

- Gaps in knowledge cause participants to misinterpret the data or limit their ability to gain insights. For instance, participants without prior knowledge of sonification drew false comparisons by directly comparing pitch values across different plots.
- No single representation is best for all tasks. The usefulness of each representation is dependent on the task, and just having access to a data representation does not mean users will find the specific representations useful.
- Only a small number of the audited top-ranked Google search results visualisations on the web (in the "Top Results" group) provide screen reader access to content, context, effective navigation, and interactive features.
- Both auditors and contextual inquiry respondents appreciated the proper use of headers to delineate between individual groups of visualisations.

- Webpages and dashboards with poor semantic structure were a barrier for discovering information related to the visualisation (source, update frequency, and download links) and potentially the visualisation itself.

Limitations

The authors identify the following limitations of current tools for web-based data visualisation:

- Web-based SVGs and dashboards are inaccessible. There is an absence of meaningful summaries and metadata.
- Poor ARIA labelling is added to HTML elements to provide additional information to assistive technologies like screen readers.
- Web pages do not support proper keyboard navigation and focus handling and contain multiple visualisations across many sections that require hundreds of interactions to read through.
- There is often an incompatibility with users' choice of screen reader.
- There are non-explicit links between data visualisations and contextual content.
- Users require proprietary software (e.g., Power BI) or plugin compatibility to consume the visualisations. They are further required to learn unique sets of keyboard interaction techniques to access and interact with visualisations.
- Pop-up blockers prevented users from perceiving the accessibility overlay of one website.
- There is also a lack of feedback during content loading for screen readers.

Survey limitations include the diversity of visual abilities within the sample, meaning users relied on different assistive technologies in different ways. All respondents were screen reader users.

Contextual inquiry limitations include potential selection bias, as participants who opted to participate might have had an interest in data accessibility, which could have affected the range of perspectives captured by the study. The contextual inquiry investigated how participants might gain insights from three Born Accessible websites, which the audit showed to have higher accessibility ratings and criteria pass rates than visualisations that appear in the top results of Google Searches. Therefore, the observations may not have captured how users might experience visualisations from more prominent websites that are less accessible.

Finally, the lack of CS educational settings can be considered a limitation of this study. However, although the study does not refer to CS education, it offers insights into the accessibility of web-based visual content.

3.2.2.4 Chart Reader

Thompson et al. (2023) present Chart Reader, a web-based accessibility engine co-designed with 10 BLV screen reader users to improve access to digital data visualisations. Over a 5-month and 3-iterations co-design process, the authors developed interactive chart features that support navigation, sonification, filtering, and textual descriptions tailored for screen reader users. The final prototype enables BLV users to explore visualisations independently using multiple modalities – text, keyboard navigation, and non-speech audio (sonification). The study contributes to a robust, flexible, and customizable system that significantly improves accessibility and understanding of visual data for BLV individuals. While the tool is not integrated into formal higher education, it sets a solid foundation for accessible data exploration, which could be easily adopted in CS courses.

The study does not apply direct pedagogical approaches, but encourages autonomous, exploratory learning through rich feedback. The evaluation of the visualisation prototypes included tasks with data exploration questions (e.g., finding trends, maximum values, performing comparisons based on the available data). Although the authors do not address classroom tools in particular, they incorporate the teaching-relevant design approaches. Iterative co-design allows for accessible data literacy and autonomous exploration of data visualisations. Furthermore, the developed tool allows screen reader users to explore line charts, multi-series charts, and stacked bar charts with structured guidance. The system builds skills in analysis and comprehension of graphical data.

Evaluation

The study employed a parallel co-design methodology, including 10 BLV screen reader users (diverse in age, expertise, screen reader type, and visual impairment onset). There were three one-on-one remote sessions (via MS Teams) spaced 4–6 weeks apart. Several visualisation prototypes were evaluated, containing different visual types presented, including a single-series line chart, a multi-series line chart, and a stacked bar chart. The example data included COVID-19 reports, currency trends, and Olympic medal counts.

Participants answered structured data questions (e.g., finding peak values, trends, performing comparisons) based on the visualisations they were given. The feedback process was video and audio recorded, and then transcribed. The feedback was coded into 5 categories: positive/negative interactions, unusual feedback, feature requests, and bugs. Each iteration introduced refinements based on previous insights. This structure enabled personalization, clear insight into user needs, and targeted iteration of accessible visualisation features.

Design participants loved the capability and flexibility to interactively read and understand visualisations and their underlying data. The study did not include any additional evaluation except the feedback obtained from design participants.

Limitations

The authors comment on how screen readers are not designed to handle spatial or hierarchical data, often represented with diagrams and charts.

A limitation of the accessible visualisation rendering engine is our predominant focus on blind users. The design almost exclusively focuses on audio representation with little supplementary visuals. Additionally, the developed prototype is more effective when used by people with a strong familiarity with screen readers, while individuals who are less experienced with screen readers could have a harder time operating them.

The developed accessible visualisation design was not evaluated with a larger group of BVI users, but only those who participated in the design.

The developed accessible visualisation designs require the understanding of key features and underlying navigation model, as well as the use of many key combinations (i.e., hotkeys). During co-design sessions, the authors walked the participants through new features or visualisations when they were introduced. However, this is not feasible in the real-world setting, and the authors argue that providing a link to the table of keyboard interactions would not be enough to help a new BLV user become familiar with the accessible visualisation designs. Additionally, the expansion of the coverage of chart types requires a mechanism to introduce new chart types to BLVIs (especially the ones they are not previously familiar with).

The Chart Reader engine currently supports rendering only three chart types: single-series line chart, multi-series line chart, stacked bar chart.

3.2.2.5 MAIDR (Multimodal Access and Interactive Data Representation)

The paper (Seo et al., 2024) introduces MAIDR (Multimodal Access and Interactive Data Representation), a system designed to make statistical visualisations such as bar plots, heat maps, box plots, and scatter plots accessible to blind users through a combination of multimodal data representations. Beyond traditional sonification and textual descriptions, MAIDR incorporates two additional modalities: braille and a review mode, offering complementary benefits. A user study with 11 blind participants demonstrated that MAIDR facilitated accurate interpretation of statistical visualisations, with participants employing various strategies to combine modalities based on their prior experiences. The study underscores the potential of integrating refreshable tactile representations with other modalities and highlights the importance of user autonomy in designing accessible data visualisations.

The user study revealed that participants utilized a range of modality combinations, such as sonification for global pattern scanning and braille for tactile structural feedback, with text used for precise data point interpretation. This multimodal integration empowered users to shift between holistic and granular exploration strategies. Participants demonstrated diverse

approaches to interacting with data, depending on prior experience, hearing sensitivity, and braille literacy.

One major insight was the contrasting exploration strategies: some participants adopted a “whole-to-part” method using sonification or braille to understand trends before accessing fine-grained data, while others preferred a “part-to-whole” approach that began with textual descriptions for orientation. Additionally, findings highlighted the potential of tactile feedback for reinforcing verbal comprehension and mitigating cognitive overload. The review mode, which provided persistent verbal information on braille displays, proved crucial for users who found spoken output too fast or hard to parse. This research emphasizes the critical role of user autonomy, modality flexibility, and device compatibility in enhancing accessibility for blind users in data visualisation contexts.

Evaluation

The study included 11 blind participants with varying backgrounds and experiences in data interpretation. All participants had some familiarity with statistical concepts and used single-line refreshable braille displays and screen readers like JAWS, NVDA, and Orca. Each study session was conducted remotely via Zoom and spanned 2.5 to 3 hours. Each session included a tutorial, a data exploration task, a usability survey, and a follow-up interview.

Participants engaged with the MAIDR system to interpret different types of statistical visualisations (bar plots, heat maps, box plots, and scatter plots). The system provided data through multiple modalities: sonification, textual descriptions, braille, and a review mode. Participants' interactions were observed through audio and screen recordings during task sessions, and their feedback was collected through subsequent interviews. Additionally, low-level action logs from participants during task sessions were collected.

Qualitative analysis of participants' strategies in combining modalities was performed. Each modality was assessed in terms of its effectiveness in conveying information. Participants answered 4–6 questions per visualisation, covering lookup, compositional, visual, and non-visual queries. Tasks were designed to evaluate how effectively users could extract insights using different modality combinations. Their interactions were logged automatically and analysed alongside video/audio recordings and interview transcripts. A mixed-methods approach was employed: action logs were transformed into aggregated state diagrams to visualize interaction patterns, while interview data were thematically coded.

The authors further evaluated the user autonomy and control in interacting with the system. The usability of the system was evaluated using the System Usability Scale (SUS) test. MAIDR scored well overall, with bar plots rated highest (81.36) and scatter plots lowest (70.25), suggesting modality learnability varied by visualisation complexity.

Limitations

One limitation of the study is the use of single-line braille displays, which constrained the tactile resolution and representation of complex graphics. Although MAIDR adapts to different display sizes, it cannot fully replicate the experience offered by multi-line or 3D tactile graphs. This limitation particularly affected visualisations like scatter plots, where representing dense point clouds on a linear display proved challenging. Additionally, the review and Braille modes could not be shown simultaneously on the same braille line due to hardware limitations, leading to some modality-switching friction. The design choices restrict the fidelity of the tactile feedback in comparison to embossed or multi-line formats.

Another limitation concerns participant diversity. All participants had high levels of braille literacy and experience with screen readers, which may not represent the broader blind population, particularly novices or low-braille users. Moreover, the controlled tasks and datasets may not fully replicate real-world data complexity or professional environments. The use of synthetic, web-based visualisations also differs from embedded charts in office documents or dashboards. Lastly, the study emphasizes four basic visualisation types and does not encompass the full range of statistical graphics (e.g., violin plots, tree maps, or interactive dashboards), which would require future extensions of the MAIDR system.

The study focused exclusively on blind users. Low-vision was not specifically addressed.

3.2.2.6 Summary and Recommendations

Data visualisation is inherently challenging for BVI individuals due to its visual nature. Tangible alternatives, such as printing charts on specialised tactile paper, exist; however, they are difficult to produce and can be costly.

Tools like Audio-Tactile Reader allows people to directly read digital content and feel out the graphs in a comparable way to the paper solution- but it allows for many more benefits, such as colour filtering (filter out visual clutter and try different presets) or zooming. It also translates digital text directly into braille.

It is possible to create these graphs in various different programming languages (such as R, as discussed in the example above), where information can be embedded directly into the graph (and image elements). This is done manually; it would mean one has to write and encode this information themselves.

There are also solutions like chart reader, which allows the creation of charts that can be easily deciphered by people using screen readers. This also would mean that the graphs have to be made and adapted to (and using) the format, which is incredibly time intensive.

MAIDR allows users to import SVG plots and provides the user with alternative ways to read them. This also requires manual adaptation.

Overall, while these tools offer promising approaches to improving accessibility, they often require significant manual effort and are not yet widely integrated into standard workflows.

3.2.2.7 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Audio Tactile Reader
- Creating Accessible Statistics in R
- Maidr/Chart Reader - Create accessible plots

3.2.3 Charts

3.2.3.1 VoxLens: Making Online Data Visualisations Accessible with an Interactive JavaScript Plug-In

Sharif et al. (2022) describe a tool VOxLens, that enhances the accessibility of online data visualisations for blind and visually impaired users. It is a JavaScript plug-in. It works with popular chart libraries (e.g., Chart.js, Google Charts, Highcharts), supports screen readers, and allows both voice and keyboard-based queries for accessibility. It offers three modes for accessing chart data: (1) a voice-based Q&A mode for verbal interaction; (2) a summary mode that reads out key information; and (3) a sonification mode that translates data into sound.

Evaluation

The evaluation shows improvements in performance and user experience. BVI users completed tasks 123% faster with VoxLens than without it, and accuracy improved by 122%. Users also reported higher satisfaction and confidence in interpreting charts. Sighted users found the tool beneficial as well, although not essential for access.

Limitations

Several limitations are identified. The tool was only tested on three chart types: bar, pie, and line. Participants were familiar with screen readers, so results may differ for novice users. The study was conducted in a controlled environment, meaning real-world performance may vary. It is also unclear whether the tool was tested with higher education CS students, as participants were general online users (Sharif et al., 2022)

3.2.3.2 Haptic 3D Surface Representation of Table-Based Data

Relief charts are a technique for representing tabular data and charts to BLV users proposed by (Braier et al., 2015)

The basic idea is to convert data into various types of 3D charts, which are then 3D printed. While similar technologies have been proposed before, this approach uses the third

dimension to represent different interface elements, such as varying bar heights to improve comprehension. Different chart types provide access to different aspects of the data. For example, a radar chart can be used to depict average rainfall over three years across multiple countries. Users can then select a country to view rainfall over time in a bar chart, or select a year to view a pie chart representing rainfall distribution across countries. These approaches are argued to improve comprehension compared to embossed paper charts. Technology similar to this has been proposed before, but this paper proposes using the third dimension to allow different interface elements to be presented to the users. For example, when presenting a bar chart, the heights of each bar can differ, which eases comprehension.

Evaluation

The evaluation of the approach indicates positive outcomes. The system was tested on 17 participants, most of whom found the relief charts to be helpful. Testing was conducted by evaluating how well participants were able to answer questions about the data.

Limitations

Several limitations of the approach are identified. The approach requires significant monetary investment in 3D printers. Although the conversion process can largely be automated, it still depends on specialised hardware.

3.2.3.3 Improving Blind Students' Access to Visual Information

Baker's (2017) PhD thesis on "Understanding and Improving Blind Students' Access to Visual Information in Computer Science Education" concluded with several findings. These include limited accessibility in popular IDEs, a preference among students for text editors and command-line tools due to their predictability and compatibility with screen readers, and a lack of standardisation in IDE accessibility. Students reported that these tools provided more control, fewer distractions, and better auditory feedback for code. The study also highlights a desire for more inclusive tools, with participants expressing the need for IDEs designed with screen reader compatibility from the outset rather than as an afterthought. The participants in the study were 15 blind graduates from the field of Computer Science.

Evaluation

The evaluation is based on qualitative findings from participants. The study draws on the experiences of 15 blind Computer Science graduates to identify key accessibility barriers and preferences in programming environments.

Limitations

The study is based on a relatively small sample size of 15 participants. In addition, participants were graduates rather than current students, which may limit the applicability of findings to current educational contexts.

3.2.3.4 Summary and Recommendations

Charts and data visualisations remain challenging for blind and visually impaired users due to their reliance on visual and spatial representations. While a range of solutions exists, these often require additional adaptation, specialised tools, or prior experience with assistive technologies.

Tools such as VoxLens demonstrate that interactive approaches, including voice interaction, sonification, and structured navigation, can significantly improve both performance and user confidence when interpreting charts. Similarly, approaches such as 3D relief charts provide alternative, tactile ways of accessing data, although these depend on specialised hardware and may not be widely available.

At the same time, several limitations persist across the reviewed work. Many tools are tested only on a limited number of chart types or with small groups of experienced users. In addition, solutions are often evaluated in controlled environments, which may not reflect real-world use. There is also limited evidence of application within higher education computer science contexts.

Overall, improving accessibility in charts requires both the integration of accessibility features into mainstream tools and the continued development of multimodal approaches that support independent exploration and interpretation of data.

3.2.3.5 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- VoxLens (JavaScript plug-in supporting voice interaction, keyboard navigation, and sonification)
- Relief charts (3D printed tactile charts for representing tabular data)
- Text editors and command-line tools (preferred by blind users for accessibility and control, as identified by Baker, 2017)

3.3 Applied and Technical Domains

3.3.1 Networks

3.3.1.1. Accessible Networking Education Using Assistive Technologies

A mix of tools were used to make industry-standard (Cisco) IT networking skills accessible to blind students. The authors redeveloped Cisco networking materials, which are used at many higher education institutions, including TU Dublin. A control group of sighted students received the same curriculum using standard materials (L. Armstrong, 2009).

The tools used included screen readers, screen enlargers, and a speech synthesizer for Linux VMWare (for network virtualisation). VoIP systems (Cisco CallManager, Ventrilo, Skype) and Braille transcription (UEBC and Computer Braille) were also used. In addition, manual teaching aids were developed, including pegboards to explain binary–hexadecimal–decimal conversions and IP addressing, and dominos and wire to illustrate network topography. The iNetSim tool was also used as a keyboard-driven network simulation tool tailored for blind students (L. Armstrong, 2009).

Evaluation/Findings

The results showed that blind students achieved equal or higher grades, although they required significantly more time. Surveys confirmed strong satisfaction with the tools, content accessibility, and instructor support. The visually impaired students required information and tasks to be organised in a linear fashion. Large amounts of information or complex data presented in tables were particularly difficult for students to interpret without error, and practical activities were also approached in a linear manner.

Repetition of concepts, materials, and practical exercises was identified as a key factor in supporting comprehension. Experiential learning was found to be highly relevant for visually impaired learners. Additional time needed to be incorporated into the teaching schedule to allow for repetition. Materials converted into Braille were largely unused, as students preferred to repeatedly listen to audio lectures and use screen readers to access textual materials (L. Armstrong, 2009).

Limitation

Several limitations were identified. Sighted and blind students were taught by different instructors and on different schedules. Visually impaired students had more classroom hours (10 versus 6 per week), which affected comparability. Descriptive alternatives for images were labour-intensive and not always sufficiently detailed. Screen readers and assistive tools had limited compatibility with Linux and Flash. The retrofitting of accessibility into mainstream Cisco materials was time-consuming and incomplete (L. Armstrong, 2009).

3.3.1.2 Summary and Recommendations

Networking can be made accessible by adapting materials into formats that are perceivable and usable for blind and visually impaired students. While this process may require additional time, it is necessary to ensure accessibility. Physical aids, such as pegboards, can be used to represent network layouts, while diagramming tools such as PlantUML can provide accessible digital representations that can be interpreted using screen readers.

3.3.1.3 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Physical Pegboards

- Making Alternative text versions of images
- Drawing graphs in PlantUML

3.3.2 Robotics

3.3.2.2 JBrick: Accessible Robotics Programming

The tool JBrick (Accessible Programming Tool Kit) was developed to address the inaccessibility of robotics programming environments, which are typically highly graphical in nature (Ludi and Jordan, 2015).

JBrick is a text-based programming interface for programming Lego Mindstorms NXT robots. It is implemented in Java to allow for cross-platform deployment. Code is written using a keyboard, supported by magnification software and, where required, mouse input. Output is provided through screen readers and refreshable Braille displays, as well as visual output.

Evaluation

The evaluation of JBrick showed that, with minimal training and appropriate assistive technology setup, students were able to independently write, test, and debug code (Ludi and Jordan, 2015).

Limitations

Several limitations were identified. Testing was not conducted in a higher education setting, but during a summer programme with teenagers (age not documented). However, participants worked in teams for 3-4 hours per day over four days, which is similar to how programming is taught in third-level settings through team-based lab sessions.

Not all accessibility challenges could be addressed within the software, particularly those related to keyboard familiarity. Participants' varying experience with screen readers and keyboard layouts also affected performance. Those less familiar with JAWS shortcuts required more attempts to activate commands, while limited keyboard skills led novice blind programmers to input extra characters, increasing the need for corrections (Ludi and Jordan, 2015).

3.3.2.3 Summary and Recommendations

Robotics can be taught to blind students using LEGO Mindstorms and JBrick, which allows students to program robots through a textual interface. However, sighted assistance is still required to verify whether the robot performs the intended actions.

3.3.2.4 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- JBrick

3.3.3 Physics and Electronics

3.3.3.2 Hands-on electricity remote teaching to a blind student during pandemic of 2020

Velloso et al. (2021) describe their experience teaching a blind university student online during the COVID-19 pandemic. This was an electronics class taught as part of a computer engineering course, so it may not be directly applicable to computer science.

The teaching approach included the following elements:

- The teaching staff developed a large number of physical devices and resources, which were sanitised and delivered to the student's home address.
- A representation of an electronic circuit using balls moving around a physical track, allowing the student to simulate the flow of electricity through touch.
- Simulation of electronic components (e.g., a resistor represented by a narrow point in the track, or a switch as a movable barrier).
- Additional devices, including a magnetic frame for drawing graphs, a Braille multimeter, and materials for measuring conductance.
- Frequent evaluation of the student's progress throughout the course.

Evaluation

The evaluation is based on the experience of a single student. The approach enabled the student to engage with hands-on learning through physical representations of abstract electronic concepts.

Limitations

Several limitations are identified. The study only covers the experience of a single student. In addition, the quantity of work and burden placed on teaching staff by developing and delivering physical materials would be significant.

3.3.3.3 Designing Accessible Adaptations for an Electronic Toolkit

Johnstone et al. (2024) present a co-design study aimed at adapting an electronic toolkit to be accessible for BLV users. The authors collaborated with BLV participants to identify barriers in existing electronic toolkits and developed adaptations to enhance accessibility. The study emphasizes the importance of inclusive design practices in creating educational tools that cater to the needs of BLV individuals.

The study incorporates the following elements:

- Electronic toolkits - the study involves modifying existing electronic toolkits to incorporate accessible features for BLV users.
- BLV participants were engaged in the design process to ensure that the adaptations meet their specific needs.
- Tactile markers and auditory cues (carried by NFC tags) were implemented to facilitate interaction with the toolkit components.

These adaptations aim to provide BLV students with hands-on experience in electronics. The electronics toolkit used for adaptation was TronicBoards.

Evaluation

User studies were conducted as one-on-one evaluation sessions that lasted approximately 90 minutes, employing a form of guided exploration. The authors conducted 8 co-design sessions with 4 participants in a one-on-one manner. The aim of the initial sessions was to identify the common challenges and needs associated with building TronicBoard circuits by BLV. The final sessions aimed to resolve the toolkit's pain points by modifying the toolkit, based on feedback from previous sessions.

The adapted electronics toolkit enhances the usability of electronic toolkits for BLV users by incorporating tactile markers and auditory cues carried by NFC tags. Engaging BLV individuals in the design process ensures that the adaptations address their specific requirements. Finally, implementing the adapted toolkits in educational settings can facilitate learning electronics for BLV students.

The usability of the adapted electronic toolkit was evaluated with a SUS questionnaire, where it achieved an average score of 80.83, which can be interpreted as "good". Overall, participants had positive usability experiences with the accessible adaptations for the toolkit.

Limitations

The developed toolkit was evaluated in one-on-one sessions, but not tested in the classroom settings, where the results might be different. Furthermore, the user study included only 4 participants. The authors acknowledge the limited number of participants and mention that all were braille readers, which is not a representative sample of the BLV population. The authors further argue that the consequence of this non-representative evaluation sample is that braille readers often possess well-developed skills for exploring and interpreting tactile materials. However, consequently, they are unable to identify whether individuals who are not proficient in braille might have perceived and interacted with the toolkit adaptations differently.

An additional limitation is the absence of a comparative study between the original and adapted electronics toolkit. The authors state that this was not performed to avoid the learning effect on users and to maintain the feasibility of the study duration (within-subject design). Additionally, the sample size was insufficient to establish a control group (between-subjects design).

A further limitation is that they adapted a single electronics toolkit.

3.3.3.4 Summary and Recommendations

Electronics can also be taught to BLI students. The course materials can be adapted with one of the tools we talked about above (like doing graphs and diagrams in plantUML). There are also alternatives to the physical pegboard-coursework, like TronicBoards, which work for both blind as well as intellectually disabled students.

3.3.3.5 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Multimodal Diagram Adaptions
- TronicBoards

3.4 Cross-Cutting and General Tools

3.4.1 General Assistive Technology

3.4.1.2 Dealing with Unseen Obstacles to Education in the Digital Age

The paper (Powell et al., 2013) documents a case study of supporting a blind undergraduate student in a Computer and Information Systems degree at Robert Morris University. It highlights barriers encountered and the technological and pedagogical strategies adopted to improve access and foster effective learning. It discusses the integration of tactile diagrams through 3D printing, screen reader utilization, accessible programming environments, and various instructional formats. The study concludes with practical recommendations aligned with Universal Design for Learning (UDL) to better serve severely visually impaired (SVI) students in higher education.

For visually impaired students, technologies such as screen readers or magnifiers can be essential for access. However, many educational materials and learning management systems are not designed with accessibility in mind. Consequently, these students face "unseen" barriers that can significantly hinder their academic performance and overall learning experience.

Moreover, the authors found that students with disabilities often encounter delayed access to essential course materials, inadequate institutional support, and untrained faculty who are

unaware of how to accommodate different needs. While institutions are legally mandated to provide equal access, enforcement is inconsistent, and proactive measures are rare. The findings emphasize that accessibility must be considered from the outset of content creation, not as an afterthought, to ensure inclusive education in the digital age. This has implications for technology design, instructional planning, and institutional policy.

Evaluation

The study used a longitudinal case study approach centred on the educational journey of a single blind undergraduate student enrolled in a Computer and Information Systems (CIS) program at Robert Morris University. This qualitative approach was chosen to monitor the student's experiences over time (spanning multiple semesters), explore real-world, context-specific interventions, and gather rich, in-depth data regarding both the student's progress and the adaptations used.

One blind undergraduate student with no light perception, enrolled in a traditional, sighted-majority CIS curriculum, the only study participant. The student was both the subject and an active contributor, reflecting on challenges and testing proposed solutions. The student was taught by one of the authors across multiple courses.

Three learning environments were compared: regular classroom setting with sighted peers, one-on-one tutorial sessions with the instructor, and phone-based sessions. This allowed the researchers to directly compare learning effectiveness, engagement, and accessibility across instructional modalities. Observational data, including direct observations from instructors during lectures and lab work, notes on screen reader behaviour, class interactions, and programming performance, was collected. Collaborative class notes were maintained by both the student and instructor to document coding challenges, screen reader anomalies, the use of tactile learning aids, and document programming examples and IDE navigation strategies.

Furthermore, the participant reported feedback on the use of specific tools like JAWS and NVDA screen readers, 3D printed tactile diagrams for ER models, arrays, and databases, Caché Studio IDE on AWS-hosted virtual machines. The student provided structured feedback (informal interviews and notes) after new accessibility tools or techniques were introduced.

The student reported difficulties in accessing PDF and Power Point files, challenges in navigating online discussion boards, and delays in receiving alternative formats of textbooks and course content. Instructors were often unaware of best practices in content accessibility or relied on institutional offices without understanding how to actively support such students.

Limitations

Focus of the study was exclusively on one blind student. Low-vision considerations were not addressed.

Additionally, since the study was not longitudinal, it cannot account for how accessibility policies or student experiences evolve over a longer academic trajectory. Another limitation lies in the reliance on qualitative observations without quantitative performance metrics or broader student/faculty surveys. The study's conclusions are based on subjective experience and interpretation.

Finally, the study is potentially outdated, since it was carried out in 2013.

3.4.1.3 Summary and Recommendations

Every teaching material should be developed with accessibility in mind. While accessibility has improved since the study, progress remains limited. It is still essential that alternatives to images are provided in all documents. Proper formatting in PDF documents (e.g., using correct headings, lists, and tables) is very important and should be considered from the outset, even if no disabled students are currently present.

Through the use of screen readers and magnifiers, more documents can now be accessed than ever before; however, this also means that all materials must be made digitally available.

3.4.1.4 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- NVDA, JAWS
- Microsoft Word and alternatives

3.4.2 Audio-Based General Assistive Technology

3.4.2.2 Supporting Accessible Data Visualisation Through Audio Data Narratives

Siu et al. (2022) propose the use of an audio-based system for presenting time-series data to BLV users by converting the data into audio waveforms.

The system operates as follows:

- The raw audio waveform is segmented using a dynamic programming-based segmentation algorithm with a cost function that evaluates the consistency, duration, and number of segments.
- Each segment is converted into an audio summary, where the pitch of the signal varies over time depending on the magnitude of the wave.
- Before each segment, users are provided with a brief natural language overview.

Evaluation

The evaluation of the system indicates positive outcomes. The approach was tested on 16 users, who reported significant improvements in comprehension.

Limitations

Several limitations are identified. Students using such a system are likely to require a substantial amount of prior training.

3.4.2.3 Visual Cues for Data Analysis Features Amplify Challenges for Blind Spreadsheet Users

The paper (Perera et al., 2024) investigates how blind screen reader users interact with spreadsheets containing multiple tables and visual data analysis features such as conditional formatting, formulas, and warnings. Through a remote study with 12 blind users, the authors identified critical accessibility barriers in spreadsheet navigation and comprehension due to heavy reliance on visual cues. Although the study is not situated directly in a higher education setting, its findings are relevant to computer science education, especially in courses involving data analysis and the use of spreadsheet tools (e.g., Microsoft Excel).

Evaluation

The authors investigated how blind screen reader users interact with spreadsheets containing multiple tables and visual data analysis features such as conditional formatting, formulas, and warnings. The study included 12 blind spreadsheet users (10 totally blind, 2 legally blind; 7 males, 5 female) with backgrounds including software engineering, education, accessibility, and management. The participants were most commonly using JAWS screen reader, followed by NVDA and Narrator.

Participants were asked to explore a real-world, structured Excel spreadsheet containing three tables embedded with data analysis features such as conditional formatting, formulas, and errors. The study was designed around a simulated workplace scenario: participants acted as employees reviewing a sales report prepared by a sighted colleague for a blind manager, and were tasked with exploring and describing the data structure and insights.

The study was conducted remotely via Zoom with screen and audio sharing. The participants were given a pen-ended exploration task and an Excel sheet containing three data tables with Conditional formatting (CF), formulas (some with errors or warnings), data bars and icon sets. They were then asked to explore and summarize the spreadsheet structure.

Upon the completion of the freeform exploration task, the participants were asked five follow-up questions about the data (e.g., regarding the present errors and warnings, CF interpretation, etc.). The questions were designed to assess their ability to interpret data-

driven features such as conditional formatting, errors, and warnings. Finally, the participants provided usability feedback and improvement suggestions.

Data from two sources (screen recordings and transcribed verbal feedback) was analysed. Thematic analysis was performed applying an inductive approach for obtaining qualitative insights. Observational data was matched to participant actions and answers.

The authors discuss the potential use of AI, and generative AI in particular, to overcome challenges faced by spreadsheet users. The authors argue that LLM-based tools hold much potential to benefit screen reader users, but they have not yet been explored in the non-visual context. However, their potential use could be in

- Identifying content (providing summaries of tables in sheets).
- Understanding the structural elements of tables (identifying the number of tables and their sizes, and providing summaries about table structures).
- Identifying and understanding visual cues (information about errors and warnings, details about formatting, etc.).
- Creating and correcting formula based on natural language instructions.

Limitations

The study only considered the first consumption of a spreadsheet generated by someone else and did not address the creation and editing of spreadsheets (apart from a formula).

A major limitation of the study is the small and relatively homogenous sample size (12 participants), which may not fully represent the broader population of blind spreadsheet users. Most participants were intermediate or advanced users, meaning that novice users or those with different screen reader configurations might experience additional challenges not captured in the study. Moreover, all participants were recruited from technologically literate groups, such as accessibility professionals or blind users familiar with Excel, limiting the generalizability of the findings to less experienced users or educational contexts.

Another limitation is the artificial nature of the spreadsheet used in the study. Although the study was designed to simulate real-world conditions, it may not reflect the complexity or diversity of real workbooks created in professional environments. Only Microsoft Excel on Windows with JAWS or NVDA was tested. Other platforms and screen readers (e.g., VoiceOver, Google Sheets) may behave differently, and insights may not transfer seamlessly across tools.

3.4.2.4 Sinter: low-bandwidth remote access for the visually-impaired

The paper (Billah et al., 2016) introduces Sinter, a novel framework designed to facilitate low-bandwidth, cross-platform remote access for visually impaired users. Traditional remote

desktop protocols often fall short in supporting screen readers across different operating systems, posing significant challenges for blind users. Sinter addresses this by introducing a platform-independent intermediate representation (IR) of a remote application's user interface (UI). This IR encapsulates platform-specific accessibility information, allowing it to be reconstructed and read on any client platform without modifying the application or the screen reader. Sinter supports a wide range of applications, including Microsoft Word and Apple Mail, and operates efficiently even over low-bandwidth connections. The system's IR-level programming model also facilitates the development of additional accessibility features, enhancing the overall user experience.

While Sinter is not explicitly designed for educational settings, its capabilities have significant implications for computer science higher education.

Sinter is designed for computer users with visual impairment, specifically for cross-platform remote access. It works by scraping snapshots of an application's GUI from a specific OS. It collects a generic, least-common-denominator intermediate representation (IR) of high-level widgets, such as text boxes and buttons, potentially transforms this IR, and ultimately renders the snapshot of the application GUI using native widgets in a proxy client on a different platform. The screen reader on the client system can read this proxy as if the remote application were running locally.

The framework supports both Windows and OS X clients and servers, as well as a web browser client, enabling broad accessibility. The developed system enables:

- Cross-platform accessibility by enabling blind users to access applications across different operating systems using their preferred screen readers, eliminating the need to learn multiple screen readers for different platforms.
- Low-bandwidth efficiency - its low-bandwidth operation ensures that users in areas with limited internet connectivity can still access necessary applications remotely.
- Integration with existing assistive technologies (screen readers), without requiring significant changes to existing infrastructure.

Evaluation

The evaluation of Sinter consisted of micro benchmarking tests, cross-platform UI rendering demonstrations, and a preliminary user study. In performance tests, the authors compared Sinter to Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP) and NVDA Remote across multiple tasks, including editing in Microsoft Word, navigating Windows Explorer, and updating dynamic UI elements. Latency and bandwidth were measured on both WAN and simulated 4G networks. Sinter demonstrated lower bandwidth usage (an order of magnitude lower than RDP) and comparable or superior latency. These results show that Sinter's IR-based approach is efficient enough for practical, everyday use.

To evaluate cross-platform remote access, Windows applications (Microsoft Word, Windows Calculator, Windows Explorer, the Windows registry editor, and the DOS command line) were accessed from OS X, and Mac applications (Apple Mail, HandBrake (a media ripping and transcoding utility), Messages, Calculator, and Contacts) were accessed from Windows. A web proxy version of Sinter was also implemented and tested with the ChromeVox browser screen reader, showing compatibility with cloud-based accessibility tools.

The authors perform a user study with 21 subjects who were blind (18/21) or had extremely low-vision (3/21), who did several simple tasks with Sinter. The authors only report that all of the 21 users responded positively to the user experience and would be interested in using Sinter again.

Limitations

The user study was only briefly mentioned in the paper, without providing any significant details about it.

Another limitation is that Sinter currently supports only one active client proxy per remote application session, restricting use in collaborative or multi-client contexts. Custom or highly graphical UI components may not translate well and are instead reduced to generic types, potentially losing information.

3.4.2.5 Summary and Recommendations

In terms of Audio-based assistive technology, the screen reader is the most effective. It requires a bit of training but is far easier to pick up, than the alternatives.

However, there are still limitations, due to bad formatting or inaccessible design of websites or documents. Tables, which are important in computer science, are still difficult to understand with screen readers if the proper accessibility measures have not been taken.

3.4.2.6 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- JAWs
- NVDA
- Narrator

3.4.3 Tactile General Assistive Technology

3.4.3.2 Improving the Accessibility of ASCII Graphics for the Blind Students

The paper (Müller and Constantinescu, 2010) addresses the challenges faced by blind students in accessing graphical content, particularly in fields of natural sciences where diagrams and visual representations are prevalent. The authors propose the use of ASCII

graphics as an accessible alternative, detailing a method for automatically extracting and transforming these graphics for tactile embossing. This approach aims to empower blind students to independently create and interpret graphical information.

The paper focuses on the utilization of ASCII graphics as a means to convey visual information in an accessible format for blind students. By converting graphical content into ASCII representations, which can then be printed using tactile embossers, students can independently explore and understand complex diagrams.

Although the authors do not consider the digital format of the generated ASCII graphics, they propose the use of the Hyperbraille display for reading and drawing ASCII graphics. The display could be used by blind students to evaluate their own graphics.

The authors provide a simple way of improving the accessibility of ASCII graphics by automatically extracting them from accessible ASCII-books and preparing them for the printout.

Evaluation

The authors describe a process of automatically extracting and transforming graphical content into ASCII format suitable for tactile embossing. While the paper outlines the theoretical framework and potential applications, it does not provide empirical data or detailed user studies to validate the effectiveness of the approach.

The automatic creation of a corpus of printable graphics increases the value of the books and lecture notes for blind students. The authors believe that ASCII graphics are a good option making graphics accessible to blind people due to their reduced learning time, platform independence, and the fact that they allow blind people to create their own graphics.

Limitations

The paper specifically addresses the needs of blind students, focusing on tactile methods of accessing graphical information. It does not explore solutions tailored for students with low-vision.

The proposed approach lacks evaluation.

3.4.3.3 Summary and Recommendations

A lot of work has been done on tactile materials: It is a very good practice to create versions of graphics such as plots or diagrams, on embossed paper, or similar media. However, these are hard to come by and can be expensive and time-consuming to create. An alternative to this would be something like a HyperBraille display, that allows users to engage with graphics through touch, via an electronic interface.

3.4.3.4 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Printing on tactile Paper
- Braille Displays

3.4.4 Haptic General Assistive Technology

3.4.4.2 Evaluation of Haptic HTML Mappings

Kuber et al. (2011) describe a method of mapping webpage layout information to BLV users using a haptic mouse.

The approach includes the following elements:

- Web page layout is generally ignored by screen readers, but is often important for comprehending a page effectively (e.g., layout may indicate the most important content).
- The paper introduces the use of a mouse with haptic feedback, which can vibrate or produce force feedback to communicate information to the user.
- An experiment is presented in which the mouse indicates image borders using an “enclosure effect” and directs users towards the centre of hyperlinks using a “spring effect”.
- Users were asked to perform tasks such as determining the layout of an unfamiliar webpage or completing a collaborative task with a sighted user.

Evaluation

The evaluation of the approach involved measuring task performance and collecting user feedback. Participants were timed to assess how long tasks took and completed questionnaires. The system was evaluated with 17 participants, although only 5 were screen reader users.

Limitations

Several limitations are identified. Users required training before using the system. The approach depends on a haptic mouse (in this case, a Logitech model), which is generally more expensive than standard devices. In addition, screen reader users are often unfamiliar with mouse interaction and may require time to become accustomed to using such devices.

3.4.4.3 Summary and Recommendations

Haptic technology shows promise in enabling users to explore layouts non-visually. However, these technologies are still under development and require further research and refinement..

3.4.4.4 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Haptic Mouse

3.4.5 Camera-Based General Assistive Technology

4.4.5.1 Note-Taker 3.0

Note-Taker 3.0 is a camera-based device designed to allow users with limited eyesight (including legally blind users) to view the blackboard or whiteboard in a classroom setting without needing assistance from a sighted note taker (Hayden et al., 2011).

The system provides the following functionality:

- Allows users to view the board (via the camera feed) and a note-taking application side-by-side on a tablet computer.
- Allows students to take their own notes, which is both empowering and is believed to lead to better learning outcomes

Evaluation

The system was tested with both second- and third-level (higher education) students. The first prototype (Note-Taker 1.0) was subject to approximately 150 hours of classroom testing, with most of the evaluation conducted on this earlier version.

Limitations

Several limitations can be identified. Most of the testing was conducted on the earlier prototype (Note-Taker 1.0), rather than the final system.

4.4.5.2 Summary and Recommendations

Camera-based assistive technologies such as Note-Taker 3.0 provide an effective way for students with limited vision to access board-based content in classroom settings. By allowing students to view the board alongside their own notes, these systems support greater independence and may contribute to improved learning outcomes.

However, the evidence base remains limited, as most evaluation was conducted on earlier versions of the system. Further testing in real-world higher education settings is required to assess long-term effectiveness and usability.

Overall, such tools highlight the importance of supporting independent note-taking and real-time access to visual teaching materials through integrated assistive technologies.

4.4.5.3 Currently Relevant Tools Identified in the Review

- Note-Taker 3.0 (camera-based system for viewing board content and taking notes simultaneously)
- Note-Taker 1.0 (earlier prototype used for extended classroom evaluation)

4 Overall Discussion and Future Work

Fifty-four papers were initially considered for this section; four were excluded, resulting in fifty papers being reviewed. Our findings point to a mix of promising developments and ongoing challenges.

Some tools and approaches stood out that are worth further exploration—for example, the combined use of multiple tools for a single subject, the VoxLens system, JBricks, user-centred design processes, the preference for text based editors for programming and the use of tactile diagrams (Crockett and Gannod, 2020; L. Armstrong, 2009; Ludi and Jordan, 2015; Sharif et al., 2022). Blind students found tools like PlantUML worked well for their needs, while also being useful to sighted students (Carruthers et al., 2023; Müller, 2012). PlantUML provides a human-readable text representation of UML diagrams that are accessible to people using a screen reader. Converting between different mathematical representations is another area that can be done in an inclusive way: for example, software to automatically convert between MathML and mathematical Braille (Mikulowski, 2022). However, there are still significant gaps and limitations (even with the above positive findings), particularly in terms of real-world application, long-term sustainability, and keeping pace with current technological developments.

In the discussion that follows, we focus on key areas where improvements are needed. These include practical challenges in implementation, especially time, limited use of recent advances in AI, and the fact that many tools—especially in maths education—are outdated or offer only partial solutions. Our findings are discussed under the following headings: Practicality, Lack of Formal Evaluation, Small Number of Volunteers, Continued Development, Artificial Intelligence and outdated tools.

4.1 Practicality

While many tools and interventions show promise in theory, putting them into practice often highlights real challenges. This paragraph looks at key barriers to implementation that come up across the literature, focusing on four common issues: the lack of real-world validation, the time and effort needed to develop accessible materials, the learning curve involved in using screen readers effectively, and the reliance on specialised hardware. These practical constraints raise important questions about how usable and sustainable these tools really are in everyday teaching and learning at higher education.

- Real-World Validation: Lacking or identified lacking in following studies (Schanzer et al., 2019)(Verde et al., 2023)(Ferrari et al., 2019)(Ludi and Jordan, 2015)(Sharif et al., 2022)
- Time taken to develop Materials: Identified in the following papers (L. Armstrong, 2009)(Ferrari et al., 2023)(Ferrari et al., 2019)(Crockett and Gannod, 2020)

- Screen Reader: Students need to learn how to use properly as a finding in the following papers (Ferrari et al., 2019), (Ferrari et al., 2023) and (Ludi and Jordan, 2015). This was of particular importance for high school students.
- Practicality Hardware dependency: Requires tactile printers and swell paper. (Crockett and Gannod, 2020).

4.2 Lack of detailed/formal evaluation

- A common issue seems to be papers that lack any type of systematic/formal evaluation to validate the proposed approach.
- Frequently, papers discuss an existing course that was not designed without accessibility in mind, and that therefore has to be adapted to facilitate a blind or visually impaired student (Carruthers et al., 2023; Velloso et al., 2021) on a best-effort basis.
- These papers report positive results, but more research is needed on alternative approaches and best practices.

4.3 Small number of volunteers for evaluation

- A related issue is evaluation of the system on very small groups of volunteers. This is common even in situations where a formal evaluation of the system is present
- For example, although the haptic feedback system proposed by Kuber et al. (2011) was tested on a group of 17 users, only 5 of them used a screen reader.
- Both (Carruthers et al., 2023) and (Velloso et al., 2021) appear to document the experience of a single student
- The SZS LaTeX editor (Melfi et al., 2018) was tested on a group of just 3 users.
- Py2UML had one tester (Verde et al., 2023) similarly (Papasalouros and Tsolomitis,

4.4. Lack of continued development of the project

- Projects are frequently developed and report positive results, but there does not appear to be any follow-up publications on the system or further refinements.
- Some concrete examples of this are the Grid-Coding editor (Ehtesham-UI-Haque et al., 2022), the time-series to audio converter proposed by Siu et al. (2022), the TangibleGrid layout system of Li et al. (2022) the relief charts proposed by Braier et al. (2015) and Py2UML (Verde et al., 2023)
- Quorum is a good example of a project that does not exhibit this pattern: it has been under continuous development since 2011.

4.5 Changes brought about by AI

- Modern generative AI is causing major disruptive changes to computer science education, and this fact isn't being reflected in the papers and approaches summarised in this report.
- There is potential for gen AI tools to be used to help BLV students
- Communicative images were proposed by (Kopecek and Oslejsek, 2011) as a technique to allow Web Ontology Language (OWL) data to be embedded into SVG images. The OWL data could then be queried by the users to get details about the contents of the images
- The authors of the paper propose crowdfunding this information about the papers (e.g., using services like Mechanical Turk)
- A lot of this process could likely be automated with modern AI -- tools to describe the contents of images already exist
- It would be useful to see if these tools are useful for BLV users, and if the use of formal ontology languages could improve the quality of these tools

4.6 Outdated Tools

This field is evolving rapidly, and several of the papers we reviewed highlight just how quickly tools can become outdated. Three examples from our review: Ribera et al. (2013), Kapperman and Sticken (2002) and Ferres and Sepulveda (2011) illustrate this point clearly in the context of mathematics accessibility.

Ribera et al.'s (2013) paper focused on comparing the accessibility of mathematical formulae produced with various editors, including Microsoft Word 2007, MathType 6.0c, and LibreOffice Math 3.3.2. While the study was thorough at the time, its reliance on now-outdated software means the methods are no longer current or widely applicable.

Kapperman and Sticken's (2002) paper describes a tutorial for the Nemeth Code, a widely used Braille system for mathematics in the U.S. The tutorial is comprehensive, with many examples and exercises. However, the download link no longer works, and the content is designed exclusively for the Braille Lite device by Freedom Scientific, significantly limiting its usefulness today.

Ferres and Sepulveda (2011) introduced MathAcc, a web-based tool that verbalizes mathematical content from Wikipedia in natural Spanish for blind users and offers color-coded visualisations for sighted users. Despite its innovative multimodal approach, the tool only supports Spanish and requires MathML-translated formulas. It depends on SnuggleTeX to convert LaTeX to MathML a process with quality issues. Moreover, the web resource is no

longer available, and Wikipedia's historical reliance on LaTeX further reduced accessibility at the time.

While each of these papers made valuable contributions to accessible mathematics, they also reflect how quickly accessibility tools can become outdated due to changing technologies and discontinued resources.

5 Conclusion

The systematic literature review shows that there is already a considerable number of technologies and teaching approaches that can improve access to Computer Science (CS) for blind and visually impaired students, but their use in real Higher Education settings is still limited. Across domains such as mathematics, programming, data visualisation, web development and other CS subjects, many tools are designed as research prototypes, with small user studies and little long-term evaluation.

Using Universal Design for Learning (UDL) as a framework helps to structure these findings and to see more clearly where current practice offers multiple means of representation, action and expression, and engagement – and where important gaps remain. In particular, there is still a strong focus on technical solutions for representation (e.g., tactile and audio formats), while questions of pedagogy, institutional support and training receive less systematic attention.

For the Access2CS project, the review provides concrete examples of technologies, methods and design principles that can inform the development of accessible CS curricula and materials, but it also underlines the need for closer cooperation between research and everyday teaching practice. Future work should include larger and more robust evaluations in real third-level contexts, stronger integration of UDL thinking at curriculum level, and a more explicit exploration of the potential and risks of AI-based tools for blind and visually impaired CS students.

At the same time, the review also highlights that much of the available research is relatively dated and often based on small, highly specific case studies. This limits the extent to which the reported findings can be generalised to today's Computer Science programmes, technologies and diverse student cohorts. Nevertheless, the systematic approach taken in this review is valuable precisely because it makes these limitations visible: it shows that the existing evidence base for accessible CS education for blind and visually impaired students is still fragmented and, in many cases, out of date. This, in turn, underlines the need for renewed, methodologically robust and participatory research that reflects current assistive technologies, learning environments and the role of emerging AI-based tools.

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7 Bibliography

Abu Doush, I., Pontelli, E., Simon, D., Son, T. C., & Ma, O. (2009, October). Making Microsoft Excel™: Multimodal presentation of charts. In *Proceedings of the 11th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility* (pp. 147–154).

Araújo, N., Amorim, F., Antunes, A., Marchi, S., Schmidt, M., Andrade, A., & Delazari, L. (2021). An experiment using the graphic variable color and the see color code on isarithmic maps accessible to blind and normally sighted people. *Boletim de Ciências Geodésicas*, 27. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1982-21702021000100006>

Archambault, D. (2011). Access to maths and science for print impaired people. In *Universal Learning Design* (p. 139).

Ariza, J. Á., & Hernández Hernández, C. (2025). A systematic literature review of research-based interventions and strategies for students with disabilities in STEM and STEAM education. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 1–31.

Armstrong, H. L. (2009). Advanced IT education for the vision impaired via e-learning. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 8(1), 243–256. <https://doi.org/10.28945/691>

Arooj, S., Zulfiqar, S., Qasim Hunain, M., Shahid, S., & Karim, A. (2020). Web-ALAP: A web-based LaTeX editor for blind individuals. In *Proceedings of the 22nd International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility (ASSETS '20)* (pp. 1–12). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3373625.3417009>

Baker, C. M. (2017). *Understanding and improving blind students' access to visual information in computer science education* (Doctoral dissertation).

Baker, C. M., Bennett, C. L., & Ladner, R. E. (2019). Educational experiences of blind programmers. In *Proceedings of the 50th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education* (pp. 759–765). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287324.3287410>

Balik, S. P., Mealin, S. P., Stallmann, M. F., & Rodman, R. D. (2013). GSK: Universally accessible graph sketching. In *Proceedings of the 44th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education* (pp. 221–226). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2445196.2445266>

Billah, S. M., Porter, D. E., & Ramakrishnan, I. V. (2016). Sinter: Low-bandwidth remote access for the visually-impaired. In *Proceedings of the Eleventh European Conference on Computer Systems* (pp. 1–16). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2901318.2901335>

Braier, J., Lattenkamp, K., Räthel, B., Schering, S., Wojatzki, M., & Weyers, B. (2014). Haptic 3D surface representation of table-based data for people with visual impairments. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 6(1), 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2700433>

Carrera-Rivera, A., Ochoa, W., Larrinaga, F., & Lasa, G. (2022). How to conduct a systematic literature review: A quick guide for computer science research. *MethodsX*, 9, 101895. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2022.101895>

Carruthers, S., Thomas, A., Kaufman-Willis, L., & Wang, A. (2023). Growing an accessible and inclusive systems design course with PlantUML. In *Proceedings of the 54th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education* (Vol. 1, pp. 249–255). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3545945.3569786>

Cervone, D., & Sorge, V. (2019). Adaptable accessibility features for mathematics on the web. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Web for All Conference (W4A '19)* (pp. 1–10). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3315002.3317567>

Crockett, A. R., & Gannod, G. C. (2020). Improving understanding of data structures for the blind with tactile media and a user-centered iterative approach. In *2020 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)* (pp. 1–8). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FIE44824.2020.9273978>

EPPI-Centre. (2006). *EPPI-Centre methods for conducting systematic reviews*. EPPI-Centre, Social Science Research Unit, Institute of Education, University of London.

Ehtesham-Ul-Haque, M., Monsur, S. M., & Billah, S. M. (2022). Grid-Coding: An accessible, efficient, and structured coding paradigm for blind and low-vision programmers. In *Proceedings of the 35th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology* (pp. 1–21). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3526113.3545620>

Fan, D., Fay Siu, A., Rao, H., Kim, G. S.-H., Vazquez, X., Greco, L., O'Modhrain, S., & Follmer, S. (2023). The accessibility of data visualisations on the web for screen reader users: Practices and experiences during COVID-19. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 16(2), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3557899>

Ferrari, C., & Hurst, A. (2021). Accessible web development: Opportunities to improve the education and practice of web development with a screen reader. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 14(2), Article 8. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3458024>

Ferrari, C., Fleet, C., Ohshiro, K., Alfaro Arias, V., Hao Xu, E., & Hurst, A. (2023). Tangible progress: Tools, techniques, and impacts of teaching web development to screen reader users. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 16(3), 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3585315>

Ferrari, C., Hurst, A., & Fitzgerald, S. (2019). Blind web development training at Oysters and Pearls Technology Camp in Uganda. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Web for All Conference* (pp. 1–10). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3315002.3317562>

Ferres, L., & Sepúlveda, J. F. (2011). Improving accessibility to mathematical formulas: The Wikipedia math accessor. In *Proceedings of the International Cross-Disciplinary Conference on Web Accessibility* (pp. 1–9). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1969289.1969322>

Fitzpatrick, D., Godfrey, A. J. R., & Sorge, V. (2017). Producing accessible statistics diagrams in R. In *Proceedings of the 14th International Web for All Conference* (pp. 1–4). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3058555.3058564>

Fusco, G., & Morash, V. S. (2015, October). The tactile graphics helper: Providing audio clarification for tactile graphics using machine vision. In *Proceedings of the 17th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers & Accessibility* (pp. 97–106). ACM.

Gough, D., Oliver, S., & Thomas, J. (2012). *An introduction to systematic reviews*. Sage.

Hayden, D. S., Astrauskas, M., Yan, Q., Zhou, L., & Black, J. A. (2011). Note-taker 3.0: An assistive technology enabling students who are legally blind to take notes in class. In *Proceedings of the 13th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility* (pp. 269–270). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2049536.2049601>

Higgins, E., Oliver, Z., & Hamidi, F. (2025). Supporting campus activism through creating DIY-AT in a social justice aligned makerspace. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 18(2), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3715965>

Isaacson, M. D., Supalo, C., Michaels, M., & Roth, A. (2016). An examination of accessible hands-on science learning experiences, self-confidence in one's capacity to function in the sciences, and motivation and interest in scientific studies and careers. *Journal of Science Education for Students with Disabilities*, 19(1), 68–75.

Jencic, M. (2012). LaTeX based notation as computer math notation for the blind. In *Proceedings of the Conference Universal Learning Design, Linz 2012: International Conference, Linz, 11–13 July 2012* (pp. 107–110). Masaryk University.

Johnstone, J., Nadeeshani, M., Chen, H., Vemula, M., Tandori, E. J., Stephens, K., Senaratne, H., Ellis, K., & Ananthanarayanan, S. (2024). Designing accessible adaptations for an electronic toolkit with blind and low vision users. In *The 26th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility* (pp. 1–15). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3663548.3675652>

Karshmer, G., Gupta, S., Geiger, C., & Weaver, C. (1998). Reading and writing mathematics: The MAVIS project. In *Proceedings of the Third International ACM Conference on Assistive Technologies (ASSETS '98)* (pp. 136–143). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/274497.274524>

Kapperman, G., & Sticken, J. (2002). A software tutorial for learning the Nemeth code of Braille mathematics. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 96(12), 855–857. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0145482X0209601205>

Kitchenham, B., & Charters, S. (2007). *Guidelines for performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering* (EBSE Technical Report). EBSE.

Kirwan, C., Costello, E., & Donlon, E. (2018). Computational thinking and online learning: A systematic literature review. In *Proceedings of the 17th European Conference on e-Learning (ECEL 2018)* (pp. 657–660). Academic Conferences and Publishing International.

Kopecek, I., & Oslejsek, R. (2011). Communicative images. In L. Dickmann, G. Volkmann, R. Malaka, S. Boll, A. Krüger, & P. Olivier (Eds.), *Smart graphics* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 6815, pp. 163–173). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-22571-0_19

Kopeček, I., Ošlejšek, R., & Plhák, J. (2012). Communicative images – New approach to accessibility of graphics. In *Proceedings of the Conference Universal Learning Design, Linz 2012* (pp. 163–173). Masaryk University.

Kruger, R., De Wet, F., & Niesler, T. (2023). Mathematical content browsing for print-disabled readers based on virtual-world exploration and audio-visual sensory substitution. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 16(2), Article 12. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3584365>

Landra, T. (2012). Tactile applications in development of the multimodal learning environment for blind students with and without learning disabilities. In *Proceedings of the Conference Universal Learning Design, Linz 2012* (pp. 131–143). Masaryk University.

Li, J., Yan, Z., Jarjue, E. H., Shetty, A., & Peng, H. (2022). TangibleGrid: Tangible web layout design for blind users. In *Proceedings of the 35th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology* (pp. 1–12). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3526113.3545627>

Ludi, S., & Jordan, S. (2015). JBrick: Accessible robotics programming for visually impaired users. In M. Antona & C. Stephanidis (Eds.), *Universal access in human-computer interaction. Access to learning, health and well-being* (pp. 157–168). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-20684-4_16

Manzoor, A., Arooj, S., Zulfiqar, S., Parvez, M., Shahid, S., & Karim, A. (2019). ALAP: Accessible LaTeX based mathematical document authoring and presentation. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–12). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300734>

Másilko, L., & Pecl, J. (2013). Mathematical algorithms and their modification for blind students. In *Conference Universal Learning Design, Brno 2013*. Masaryk University.

Masilko, L., & Pecl, J. (2013). Mathematical algorithms and their modification for blind students. In *Conference Universal Learning Design, Brno 2013*. Masaryk University.

Melfi, G., Müller, K., Schwarz, T., Jaworek, G., & Stiefelhagen, R. (2020, April). Understanding what you feel: A mobile audio-tactile system for graphics used at schools with students with visual impairment. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–12). ACM.

Melfi, G., Schölch, L., Schwarz, T., Müller, K., & Stiefelhagen, R. (2022). Audio-Tactile Reader (ATR): Interaction concepts for students with blindness to explore digital STEM documents on a 2D haptic device. In *2022 IEEE Haptics Symposium (HAPTICS)* (pp. 1–6). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HAPTICS52432.2022.9765568>

Mikulowski, D. (2022). Support for teaching mathematics of the blind by sighted tutors through multisensual access to formulas with Braille converters and speech. In *Proceedings of the*

30th ACM International Conference on Multimedia (pp. 1552–1560). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3503161.3548425>

Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & The PRISMA Group. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement. *PLOS Medicine*, 6(7), e1000097. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000097>

Moore, M., & Urness, T. (2024). Inclusive practices and universal design in the computer science classroom. *Journal of Computing Sciences in Colleges*, 39(6), 93–102.

Mountapmbeme, A., Okafor, O., & Ludi, S. (2022). Addressing accessibility barriers in programming for people with visual impairments: A literature review. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 15(2), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3507469>

Moured, O., Baumgarten-Egemole, M., Müller, K., Roitberg, A., Schwarz, T., & Stiefelhagen, R. (2024, March). Chart4Blind: An intelligent interface for chart accessibility conversion. In *Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces* (pp. 504–514). ACM.

Müller, K. (2012). How to make Unified Modeling Language diagrams accessible for blind students. In K. Miesenberger, A. Karshmer, P. Penaz, & W. Zagler (Eds.), *Computers helping people with special needs* (pp. 186–190). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-31522-0_27

Müller, K., & Constantinescu, A. (2010). Improving the accessibility of ASCII graphics for the blind students. In K. Miesenberger, J. Klaus, W. Zagler, & A. Karshmer (Eds.), *Computers helping people with special needs* (pp. 439–442). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-14100-3_65

Murphy, E., Bates, E., & Fitzpatrick, D. (2010). Designing auditory cues to enhance spoken mathematics for visually impaired users. In *Proceedings of the 12th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility* (pp. 75–82). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1878803.1878819>

Omiegbe, O. (2024). Artificial intelligence in higher education: Bridging the gap for students with disabilities. *British Journal of Education*, 12(12), 38–50.

Onishi, J., & Ono, T. (2012). Vision interaction software for the blind. In *Proceedings of the Conference Universal Learning Design, Linz 2012* (pp. xx–yy). Masaryk University.

Papasalouros, A., & Tsolomitis, A. (2015, October). A direct TeX-to-Braille transcribing method. In *Proceedings of the 17th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers & Accessibility (ASSETS '15)* (pp. 373–374). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2700648.2811376>

Pavliček, R., & Kabelka, R. (2012). Perceptibility and understandability of documents in the internet. In *Proceedings of the Conference Universal Learning Design, Linz 2012* (pp. xx–yy). Masaryk University.

Perera, M., Lee, B., Choe, E. K., & Marriott, K. (2024). Visual cues for data analysis features amplify challenges for blind spreadsheet users. In *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–16). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642753>

Periša, M., Peraković, D., & Remenar, V. (2012). Guidelines for developing e-learning system for visually impaired. In *Proceedings of the Conference Universal Learning Design, Linz 2012* (pp. xx–yy). Masaryk University.

Powell, V. J. H., Sirinterlikci, A., Zomp, C., Johnson, R. S., Miller, P., & Powell, J. C. (2013). Dealing with unseen obstacles to education in the digital age. [*Journal or conference information unavailable*].

Race, L., Fleet, C., Montour, D., Yazzolino, L., Salsiccia, M., Ferrari, C., Wells-Jensen, S., & Hurst, A. (2023). Designing while blind: Nonvisual tools and inclusive workflows for tactile graphic creation. In *The 25th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility (ASSETS '23)* (pp. 1–14). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3597638.3614546>

Ribera, M., Centelles Velilla, M., Huélamo Segura, A., Splendiani, B., & Salse, M. (2013). Evaluating solutions to process, view, and listen mathematical formula within an accessible context. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference Universal Learning Design*. Masaryk University.

Schanzer, E., Bahram, S., & Krishnamurthi, S. (2019). Accessible AST-based programming for visually-impaired programmers. In *Proceedings of the 50th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education (SIGCSE '19)* (pp. 773–779). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287324.3287499>

Schanzer, E., Bahram, S., & Krishnamurthi, S. (2020). Adapting student IDEs for blind programmers. In *Koli Calling '20: Proceedings of the 20th Koli Calling International Conference on Computing Education Research* (pp. 1–5). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3428029.3428051>

Seo, J., Xia, Y., Lee, B., McCurry, S., & Yam, Y. J. (2024). MAIDR: Making statistical visualisations accessible with multimodal data representation. In *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–22). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642730>

Sharif, A., Wang, O. H., Muongchan, A. T., Reinecke, K., & Wobbrock, J. O. (2022). VoxLens: Making online data visualisations accessible with an interactive JavaScript plug-in. In *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–19). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491102.3517431>

Siu, A., Kim, G. S.-H., O'Modhrain, S., & Follmer, S. (2022). Supporting accessible data visualisation through audio data narratives. In *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–19). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491102.3517678>

Stefik, A., Ladner, R. E., Allee, W., & Mealin, S. (2019). Computer science principles for teachers of blind and visually impaired students. In *Proceedings of the 50th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education (SIGCSE '19)* (pp. 766–772). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287324.3287453>

Stöger, B., Miesenberger, K., Neuper, W., Wenzel, M., & Neumayr, T. (2022). Designing an inclusive and accessible mathematical learning environment based on a theorem prover. In K. Miesenberger, G. Kouroupetroglou, K. Mavrou, R. Manduchi, M. Covarrubias Rodriguez, & P. Penáz (Eds.), *Computers helping people with special needs* (pp. 47–55). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-08648-9_7

Thompson, J. R., Martinez, J. J., Sarikaya, A., Cutrell, E., & Lee, B. (2023). Chart Reader: Accessible visualisation experiences designed with screen reader users. In *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '23)* (Article 802, pp. 1–18). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3544548.3581186>

Velloso, M., Arana, M., Acioly, V., & Santos, A. C. F. (2021). Hands-on electricity remote teaching to a blind student during pandemic of 2020. *Physics Education*, 56(5), 055027. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6552/ac10bb>

Verde, A., Alves, L., Fraga, L., & Soares, L. (2023). Py2UML: A tool for visually impaired students to build UML diagrams from Python coding. In *Proceedings of the XXXVII Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering* (pp. 491–496). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613372.3613418>